

Next Generation AI-Supported System Testing for Railway Control Systems

– Technical report –^{*}

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Abstract. We use the **SC**enario **S**pecification **L**anguage (SCSL) for automated generation of system-level tests of railway control systems. As system under test (SUT), a small railway station with a modern interlocking system (virtual signals, radio-based communication between trains and interlocking) is used. In comparison to “classical” model-based testing where comprehensive behavioural models of the SUT are required, scenario-based test specifications usually have considerably lower complexity. On the downside, very many scenario specifications need to be created to produce sufficiently many tests covering all system-level verification objectives (e.g. coverage of routes, different sequencing of trains traversing the railway network). We therefore propose to use generative pre-trained transformers (GPTs) to perform this “mass production” of system tests. This production can be based on (1) a small number of system test templates, one for each class of tests to be performed, (2) a set of rules guiding the GPT during the production process, and (3) a set of short verbal task descriptions, each serving as a specification for the GPT to generate a whole collection of similar system tests. We discuss low-effort options for validating the generated tests, ensuring that potential errors produced by GPTs during test generation are uncovered.

Keywords: Railway control systems, Generative Pre-trained Transformers, System Testing, Scenario-based Testing

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1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

This paper presents a novel approach to system testing of railway control systems. We advocate automated *scenario-based testing* using the **SC**enario **S**pecification **L**anguage (SCSL) [15] for this purpose: in scenario-based testing (SBT), the stimuli accepted by the system under test (SUT) and the expected SUT reactions need only be described as far as relevant for the test under consideration. Consequently, test specifications are usually less complex than reference models in model-based testing (MBT), where the *comprehensive* behaviour of the SUT needs to be described in a model.

The system tests considered in this paper focus on sections of a railway network that are controlled by one interlocking system (IXL). The IXL has a table of routes that can be allocated to trains for traversing the network section. The responsibilities of the IXL comprise the safe allocation of routes preventing train collisions and de-railing due to erroneous point positions and their resolution (i.e. deallocation) after trains have exited the routes.

Scenario-based testing, however, comes with a downside: Since behavioural scenario specifications are test-specific, different scenarios need to be enumerated for covering all relevant situations. For example, a scenario checking that trains can allocate and de-allocate a given route controlled by the IXL needs to be reincarnated for all routes of the specified interlocking table. This is where MBT performs better: Since the reference model captures all possible behaviours, MBT test generation algorithms can automatically produce tests for all routes since the latter are captured by the comprehensive model.

To make up for this disadvantage, we propose to use *generative pre-trained transformers (GPTs)* that use (1) a manually designed scenario specification serving as template, (2) a set of generation rules, and (3) a verbal description of the range of enumerations to be produced and generate the scenario incarnations in an automated way.

1.2 Test Scenario Specification With SCSL

The Scenario Specification Language SCSL has been designed by the authors to support automated testing of control systems. It is intended as an alternative to MBT, where – according to our practical experience with applications in industry [14] – the need to elaborate comprehensive formal models of the expected SUT behaviour is frequently considered to be too cumbersome by practitioners.

The SCSL language elements consist of basic types, object types and elementary scenario types. Global variables and constants can be declared using basic types. Instances of object types and the interfaces between instances are captured in a collaboration specification and can be dynamically changed during runtime. A test schedule specifies the instances of elementary scenario specifications and their execution order. The scenario instances act on and monitor the

interfaces of the objects involved. Scenario instances execute while their execution state variable `active` is `true`. Scenario-termination is indicated by setting `active` to `false`. A global variable `EoT` is initially set to `false`. When `EoT` is set to `true` (this can be done by any scenario instance), the whole test execution terminates, even if some scenario instances are still active. The test verdict is initially undefined. Any violation of a specification formula observed by any elementary scenario instance changes the verdict to `fail`, and this cannot be changed until end-of-test. If the verdict is still undefined at end-of-test, this indicates that no specifications were violated during test execution, so the verdict becomes `pass`.

The SCSL characteristics distinguishing the language from other scenario-based modelling formalisms are: (1) Object types are just specified by their interfaces, it is not required to provide comprehensive behavioural specifications. Instead, (2) situation-specific behaviour to be observed in a test execution is modelled in elementary scenarios referencing the objects involved. (3) Behavioural specifications in elementary scenarios combine declarative and imperative specification styles to facilitate the description of expected SUT behaviour in a given test. (4) Compound test scenarios are created by sequential and parallel composition of elementary scenarios. (5) Objects and their interfaces are dynamically created, deleted or rewired during runtime, using collaboration specifications. (6) The behavioural semantics of SCSL specifications is based on cyclic execution models for sub-components of the SUT and a finite-trace interpretation of LTL [7].

Unlike many scenario specification languages designed for specific domains⁴, the SCSL is a wide spectrum language. Domain-specific knowledge may be encapsulated in elementary scenarios exporting information about physical laws or applicable rules by means of their interfaces, similar to constraint blocks and parametric diagrams in SysML 1.5 [11].

We explain SCSL syntax and semantics on-the-fly in this paper when introducing the system test specifications. The details of SCSL have been specified in a technical report [16].

1.3 System Test Objectives

Generally, system tests are performed to verify that the components of the SUT interact correctly, so that the expected emergent properties⁵ are fulfilled. In safety-critical contexts, individual components are subjected to hardware-software integration tests, software tests and a variety of further verification activities that need to be concluded before the system tests are performed. The overall verification approaches are regulated by standards, such as the so-called CENELEC standards [4,3,5,2] applicable in the railway domain.

⁴ Such as, for example, the ASAM OpenScenario language designed for modelling and testing in the automotive domain, <https://www.asam.net/standards/detail/openscenario/>.

⁵ These are the system-related requirements that cannot be attributed to an individual component, but result from the interaction between the latter.

In the system tests considered in this paper, the following emergent properties need to be verified:

1. All routes specified in the IXL table (Fig. 1) can be allocated. It is ensured that trains receive their permission for route traversal only after all points along the route have been locked in their correct route-specific position. Routes are properly released after train traversal.
2. No conflicting routes are simultaneously allocated to requesting trains.
3. Different safe sequencings of trains simultaneously traversing the railway network on different routes are possible. This means that conflicting routes can be allocated in any order and that trains on non-conflicting routes can proceed concurrently and independently.
4. For checking robustness, safe IXL decisions need also to be tested in undesired constellations, such as, for example, two trains requesting routes that would lead to a front-to-front collision. This constellation could not be resolved by the IXL by safe sequencing of movement authorities, so a deadlock situation occurs where none of the trains gets an MA.

Individual system tests can be classified according to these objectives. The test objectives induce the following *test classes*:

Class 1: Route allocation tests. These tests show that all routes specified in the IXL table can be allocated and are properly released after route traversal.

Class 2: Conflict Tests. It is verified that no conflicting routes can be simultaneously allocated to different trains. These test also verify that conflicting routes can be allocated after the first train has traversed the conflicting route segments.

Class 3: Safe Sequencing Tests. It is verified that different safe sequencings of trains traversing the network are possible.

Class 4: Robustness Tests. It is verified that unwanted train constellation and route requests leading to deadlock situations still remain safe.

1.4 Main Contributions

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first approach to apply GPTs to system test generation in the railway control systems domain. The objective is not to replace formal specification and validation techniques by natural-language processing, but to integrate GPT-based generation into a verification workflow where the safety-relevant semantic decisions remain under human control.

The main contributions of this paper are as follows.

1. We show that SCSL is a suitable scenario-based specification language for railway control systems. Previous applications of SCSL focussed on the domain of autonomous robots [15]. The examples in this paper demonstrate that SCSL can also be applied effectively to railway interlocking scenarios involving route requests, movement authorities, route locking, train movements, and conflicting route allocations.

2. We demonstrate that GPTs are well suited to automatically create complete system test specifications by instantiating formally defined scenario, collaboration, and scheduling templates. In contrast to approaches where a GPT is requested to synthesise complete formal specifications directly from natural-language requirements, the GPT is used here for the more constrained task of systematically enumerating the members of a given test class under rule-based guidance.
3. We describe a review-based preparation process for GPT-supported test generation. Before the actual generation step, the GPT is requested to analyse the correctness and clarity of the elementary scenario types, the test-specific scenario templates, the collaboration and scheduling templates, and the rules for complete test classes. This review phase reduces ambiguities in the generation guidelines and was decisive for the correctness of the generated tests reported in the evaluation.
4. We present a validation concept for automatically generated system tests. The validation measures are designed to detect critical errors in generated tests during the test execution phase. As a consequence, errors in GPT-generated test specifications are unlikely to lead to erroneous safety-relevant test outcomes. Their main effect is a reduction of productivity, because detected failures have to be analysed and the generation guidelines have to be improved.
5. We evaluate the practical effectiveness of the approach on several railway interlocking test classes. The generated system tests were correct with respect to the specified generation rules, while the effort for generating and reviewing them was considerably lower than for a manual development of the same test procedures.

Overall, the paper proposes a workflow where humans define and review the semantic core of the tests, while the GPT performs the repetitive and error-prone instantiation work. This separation of concerns allows GPT-based generation to be used in a safety-related verification context without relying on the GPT as an unvalidated source of correctness.

1.5 Related Work

Scenario-based testing [9] and associated scenario specification formalisms, see e.g. [6], have been suggested and applied to domains such as Autonomous Robotics [15] and Automated Driving [10]. In the railway sector, Otela et al.[19] propose a structured, scenario-driven closed-loop simulation framework (built on OpenRails and Traffic Sequence Charts) to systematically test and validate highly automated railway systems and apply it to a level crossing example.

Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly being explored and adopted across industries as a promising approach to enhance efficiency, decision-making, and automation. In the railway sector, the use of AI in system components has been proposed for smart traffic management, predictive maintenance, and automated train control [17]. AI can also be used for supporting software development.

In this paper we suggest to use GPTs for mass generation of system tests for railway control systems. In [12], the authors provide a comparative evaluation of how well the Large Language Models (LLMs), GPT-4, Claude, and Gemini can transform user requirements into structured product requirements and generate corresponding test cases within the context of railway signalling. To this end they use an imaginary railway product: a track surveillance drone. The evaluation criteria for the output of the models are: completeness, correctness, consistency, and traceability across multiple tasks. The paper concludes that LLMs show strong potential for assisting in requirements engineering and test case generation, but they must be integrated with validation processes, expert review, and domain-specific tuning to be safely and effectively used.

1.6 Overview

In Section 2, a simple railway network and its route table are described. This serves as a sample SUT in this paper. In Section 3, re-usable basic types, object types, and elementary scenario types are presented. These types, respectively instances thereof, occur in all system test specifications. In Section 4, templates for test-specific elementary scenarios are presented, together with instantiation rules for template parameters. These templates are instantiated by a GPT to create specific system tests. The templates are in correspondance with the different test classes defined above. In Section 5, the general system test structure usable for all test classes is explained. The SCSL syntax and semantics is explained on-the-fly while presenting the test specifications. The generation rules for creating complete system tests are given in Section 6. In Section 7, we describe how the generated test parts can be effectively validated. In Section 8, we comment on the effectiveness of the GPT-based test generation approach. A conclusion is presented in Section 9. The generated system tests are documented in Appendix A.

2 Railway Network and Interlocking Table

The system tests to be elaborated are to be executed on the railway network shown in Fig. 1 which shows a simple train station network with two tracks for boarding trains, and two single-track segments to enter/leave the station in UP or DOWN direction.

The *marker boards* mb10, . . . mb15 are *virtual signals*: they mark the beginning or the end of one of the routes captured in the *interlocking table* (Table 1). Trains obtain *movement authorities (MA)* to proceed along routes up to their last elements. The trains stop there, since they detect that their position is at the end of their MA. Therefore, physical signals are not necessary.

Fig. 1: Train station railway network for system testing.

 Table 1: Interlocking table $ixlTbl[11]$.

id	from	to	dir	elems	pp	conf
1	b10	t12	UP	b10.t10.t11.t12	t11:plus	{1, 3, 5, 6, 8, 10}
2	t12	t14	UP	t12.t13.t14	t13:plus	{2, 5, 4, 6, 7}
3	b10	t20	UP	b10.t10.t11.t20	t11:minus	{1, 3, 6, 7, 8, 10}
4	t20	t14	UP	t20.t13.t14	t13:minus	{2, 4, 5, 7, 8}
5	b14	t12	DOWN	b14.t14.t13.t12	t13:plus	{1, 2, 4, 5, 7}
6	t12	t10	DOWN	t12.t11.t10	t11:plus	{1, 2, 3, 6, 8}
7	b14	t20	DOWN	b14.t14.t13.t20	t13:minus	{2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 9}
8	t20	t10	DOWN	t20.t11.t10	t11:minus	{1, 3, 4, 6, 8}
9	t14	b14	UP	t14.b14		{7, 9}
10	t10	b10	DOWN	t10.b10		{1, 3, 10}

id : route identification (id = 0 means “no route”)
from : start track element where train still has MA
to : last track element on route
elems : sequence of track elements (including from/to)
pp : point positions required for route
conf : set of conflicting routes

A route r_2 can be *allocated* to a train t_1 if (1) the train is already travelling on a route r_1 whose last element coincides with the first element of route r_2 , that is,

$$ixlTbl[r_1].to = ixlTbl[r_2].from, \quad (1)$$

(2) all points on the route are in the position specified in $ixlTbl[r_2].pp$, and
 (3) all elements of route r_2 are unoccupied, with the exception that t_1 itself may

reside already on the first element of r_2 since it has reached the last element of r_1 . (4) Conflicting routes⁶ can never be simultaneously allocated to requesting trains with one exception that allows for sequential release as explained below.

We do not consider flank protection [13] in the present paper. The reason is that the small station topology presented here as running example does not contain the typical infrastructure elements that give rise to flank-protection requirements. In particular, there are no connected points allowing a train or shunting movement to cross from one of two parallel tracks into the path of another movement. Such point configurations are among the most common sources of flank-protection constraints. While other flank-protection situations exist, modelling them would require a richer infrastructure topology than the one used here. Moreover, the example is restricted to a station area with comparatively low movement speeds, where the need for flank protection depends strongly on the concrete infrastructure layout, permitted movements, and operational rules. For these reasons, flank protection is deliberately excluded from the present case study and left for future work on larger and more complex station layouts.

Observe that for two connected routes, the last element of one route is always the same as the first element of another. For the case described by Equation (1), route r_1 is *resolved* when the train has reached and completely resides on segment $ixlTbl[r_1].to$. It is assumed that the last element of a route is never a point and always large enough to contain the whole train.

The IXL controlling route allocations and releases is expected to support *sequential release*, implementing the following rules: (1) Conflicting routes can never be *simultaneously* allocated to requesting trains. (2) If routes r_1 and r_2 are in conflict and train t_1 has already allocated r_1 , route r_2 may be allocated for another train t_2 as soon as t_1 has traversed the conflicting track sections, that is, the track elements shared by r_1 and r_2 .

Observe, however, that for the small network discussed here, a train having traversed the conflicting elements of two different routes has already reached its route end, so that the route is resolved anyway. For example, if a train t_1 travels on route 1 and another wishes to allocate route 8, the conflicting elements are $\mathfrak{t}10$ and $\mathfrak{t}11$. After t_1 has traversed these two elements, it already resides in segment $\mathfrak{t}12$ which is the end of route 1. Therefore, the IXL releases route 1 in any case before route 8 can be allocated to another train.

Observe further that if train t_1 is already travelling on some route r and another train t_2 also requests allocation of r , this can only happen *after* t_1 has left the last element of r , since the allocation rules require that all elements but the first of r must be unoccupied before the route can be allocated to t_2 .

⁶ Recall that two routes are in conflict if they share one or more track elements. There is one exception to this rule: two connected routes in the same direction are *not* in conflict if only the last element of the first route coincide with the start element of the second.

3 Re-usable Test Specification Parts

An SCSL system test specification usually consists of reusable specification parts and test-specific parts: The former comprise elementary types, global constants, object types, and a subset of elementary scenario types. These are presented in this section. The latter comprise test-specific scenario types and the proper system test specifications consisting of collaborations and schedules. To facilitate the automated generation of test-specific parts by GPTs, templates are provided defining the general structure of test-specific scenarios, collaborations, and schedules. This is described in the subsequent sections.

3.1 Basic Types and Global Variables

The track element identifiers are introduced as an enumeration type

```
enum ElementId{b10, t10, t11, t12, t13, t14, t20, b14}.
```

Enumerations are interpreted as integers, just as in the C programming language, so `b10` carries value zero and `b14` the value seven.

Integer constants `const TMAX = 6` and `const RMAX = 10` denote the maximal number of trains and routes, respectively, that are used in system tests. Route identifiers are specified by basic type `type RouteId = 0..RMAX`. Train identifiers are introduced similarly as basic type `type TrainId = 0..TMAX-1`.

Enumeration

```
enum PointStatus {plus, minus, undef}
```

denotes point states, value `plus` representing the straight point position. Point `t11`, for example, connects segments `t10` and `t12` when in `plus` position. To simplify interfacing with the IXL, linear segments also have a position which is always `plus`.

The *interlocking Table (IXL-table)* 1 is introduced as the main global constant `ixlTbl []` used in all system tests. It is typed as an array indexed over route identifiers `1..RMAX` whose elements are structures with components that can be addressed by their names `from`, `to`, `elems`, `pp`, `conf`, as shown in Table 1.

For measuring test coverage (see elementary scenario type *CoverageObserver()* specified below), a directed graph structure relating routes to each other by means of different edge types is introduced. The *coverage graph* $C = (N, E)$ is used by the coverage monitor as a global variable, and node and edge labels are marked as ‘covered’ during test execution when the associated route relationships have been tested. Graph C is maintained as a persistent data structure across all tests of a system test suite. After the test suite has been executed, the coverage information is evaluated and checked for completeness. Graph C and its initialisation at the beginning of a test suite execution are now described formally.

The *nodes* N of C consist of the route identifiers defined in the IXL table, so

$$N = \{1, 2, \dots, 10\}.$$

A *node labelling function* $c_N : N \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ is introduced and initialised by $c_N(r) = \mathbf{false}$ for all $r \in N$ at the beginning of the test campaign. During test suite execution, a function value $c_N(r)$ is changed to \mathbf{true} as soon as route r has been allocated by the IXL for the first time to an arbitrary train. Then $c_N(r)$ stays \mathbf{true} until the end of the test campaign.

The *edges* E of C consist of all route pairs, that is,

$$E = (N \times N).$$

By definition, E contains all pairs of routes that could (safely or hazardously) be allocated to two trains. Allocations need not always be simultaneous (e.g. (r, r) represents the case where first one train obtains MA for route r , and another train requests an MA for r a bit later, while the first train is still traversing r).

Two edge labelling functions are introduced. The first is $cl_E : E \rightarrow \{2, 3, 4\}$ and associates each edge with a test class. This function is initialised once and remains constant over the whole test suite execution. For example, $cl_E(r, r) = 2$ for all $r \in N$ since every route is in conflict with itself, and succeeding trains need to wait for an allocation of r until a preceding train has left r completely. Therefore, edge (r, r) should be covered by a route conflict test, so it belongs to Class 2.

If two different routes r_1, r_2 are in conflict but a suitable ordering of MA assignments can resolve the conflict then $cl_E(r_1, r_2) = 2$. Function value 2 is set, since a Class 2 test where first r_1 is allocated to some train and another train requests allocation of r_2 while r_1 is still being traversed needs to be executed. The edge in the other direction can be classified by $cl_E(r_2, r_1) = 3$, since first allocating r_2 and afterwards requesting r_1 while r_2 is still being traversed can be considered as a sequencing test (Class 3), when successful coverage of (r_1, r_2) has already shown that the IXL detects conflicts between r_1 and r_2 and prevents simultaneous route allocation. This asymmetric classification is a coverage convention, not an asymmetry of the underlying route-conflict relation. Moreover, $cl_E(r_1, r_2) = 3$ is set for all pairs of non-conflicting routes, since these pairs exercise admissible combinations of route allocations and therefore belong to the sequencing and coexistence tests rather than to conflict or robustness tests.

If two different routes r_1, r_2 are in conflict but the conflict cannot be resolved since any sequence of route allocations would lead to a collision, a deadlock situation occurs: It must be ensured that the IXL assigns MAs neither to the first nor to the second train. This is an unwanted constellation of trains, so testing it represents a robustness test. Therefore, $cl_E(r_1, r_2) = cl_E(r_2, r_1) = 4$ is set.

The second edge labelling function $c_E : E \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ is used to mark whether some edge (r_1, r_2) has been covered in one of the tests. Just as the node coverage function c_N , it is initialised by $c_E(r_1, r_2) = \mathbf{false}$ for all $(r_1, r_2) \in E$. For edges with classification $cl_E(r_1, r_2) \in \{2, 3\}$, $c_E(r_1, r_2)$ is set to \mathbf{true} if first r_1 is allocated to some train and then, while this train still traverses r_1 , another train requests MA for r_2 . For edges with classification $cl_E(r_1, r_2) = 4$, MAs can never be awarded to any of the trains involved. Therefore, these edges are marked as covered as soon as both trains *request* MA for the two routes.

Including the labelling functions, the full coverage graph structure is now represented as

$$C = (N, E, c_N, cl_E, c_E)$$

and handled as a persistent, mutable global variable. Graph C is read and written only by scenario `CoverageObserver()` specified below.

3.2 Object Types

SCSL object types are similar to classes as defined in programming languages like Java. In contrast to classes, however, they are mainly used to specify interfaces. Behaviour is usually defined in elementary scenario types as shown below.

The Interlocking is represented by object type

Listing 1: Interlocking Object Type.

```

1 object type Ixl(in req : RouteId[TMAX], in occ :  $\mathbb{B}$ [ElementId],
   in ptSts : PointStatus[ElementId], out ptCmd : PointStatus[ElementId],
   out ma : ElementId[TMAX] )
2 end type

```

Input *req* is an array of route identifiers indexed over train numbers, so that *req[tid]* represents the request of train *tid* to traverse route number *req[tid]*, value zero representing “no route request by train *tid*”. Boolean input array *occ* is indexed over track element ids⁷, *occ[id] = true* indicating that element *id* is occupied by a train. Input array *ptSts* is indexed over element identifiers and contains the actual point positions for elements that are points. Output array *ptCmd* contains the *requested* point states specified by the IXL for a route to be allocated for a train. Output array *ma* is indexed over train identifiers and contains the track element representing the end of movement authority (MA) of the associated train. All trains have at least an MA for the track element they are residing on. As soon as a route *r* has been allocated for train *tid*, *ma[tid]* is set by the IXL to the last element of that route, that is, to *ixlTbl[r].to*.

Trains are instantiated from object type

Listing 2: Train Object Type.

```

1 object type Train(in pos : ElementId, in ma : ElementId, out req : RouteId )
2 end type

```

Input *pos* contains the actual position of a train represented here for simplicity as the track element identifier the head of the train is residing on⁸. Input *ma* contains the train’s current MA value communicated by the IXL. Output *req* contains the train’s actual route request, value zero indicating “no request”.

⁷ As in the C programming language, enumeration values can be interpreted as integers.

⁸ A more refined position indicator would be the actual position along the track, measured in metres. The input is provided by satellite position-

Segments are linear track elements; they communicate their “occupied / unoccupied” information to the IXL.

Listing 3: Segment Object Type.

```
1 object type Segment(out occ :  $\mathbb{B}$ )
2 end type
```

Points accept commands from the IXL to set a specific position and output their “occupied / unoccupied” status as well as their actual position (plus or minus).

Listing 4: Point Object Type.

```
1 object type Point(in ptCmd : PointStatus, out occ :  $\mathbb{B}$ , out ptSts : PointStatus )
2 end type
```

Auxiliary Object Route Manager is used as a data container for allocated routes; the container is denoted by *ar* and can be read or written to. Boolean array *createTrainCnd* contains flags set and read by elementary scenario instances to synchronise incoming trains with other test activities. Array *maReqCnd* is used in an analogous way to synchronise requests for MA. An instance of *RouteMgr()* is used for the support of elementary scenario instances coordinating the test executions.

Listing 5: Container Object Storing Allocated Routes.

```
1 object type RouteMgr(inout ar : P(RouteId),
2 inout createTrainCnd :  $\mathbb{B}[\text{TMAX}]$ , maReqCnd :  $\mathbb{B}[\text{TMAX}]$ )
3 end type
```

3.3 Elementary Scenario Types

Scenario types declare interfaces consisting of references to instances of object types and auxiliary parameters with basic types that serve to configure the behaviour of scenario instances. All interface parameters are inputs: scenario instances write only to the parameters of objects that were referenced in the parameter list. The test schedule described in Section 5.2 specifies when instances of elementary scenarios become runnable. The actual execution of such an instance, however, commences when a specified pre-condition becomes true. The behaviour of a scenario instance is specified by

1. an LTL specification referring to the parameters of objects referenced in the scenario interface, further interface parameters, and auxiliary variables during scenario-internal actions,

ing systems like GALILEO (https://www.esa.int/Applications/Satellite_navigation/Galileo/What_is_Galileo) and refined by the train’s onboard odometry unit.

2. an initial action introducing and initialising auxiliary variables, and
3. condition action specifications similar to transition labels in UML or SysML state machines [11].

Incoming Trains. The following elementary scenario type specifies how incoming trains entering the network during test execution are created and registered in the collaboration specification (collaborations are explained in Section 5.1).

Listing 6: Scenario type for placing incoming trains.

```

1 elementary scenario IncomingTrain( idx : TrainId, c : collaboration,
2                                     b : Segment, rmgr : RouteMgr )
3 precondition b ∈ {b10, b14} ∧ ¬b.occ ∧ rmgr.createTrainCnd[idx];
4 spec X(b.occ ∧ c.tr[idx] ≠ null) ∧ XX¬active;
5 initact frame := ∅;
6         c.create(tr[idx](pos = b, ma = b, req = 0));
7         c.create(interface from tr[idx].req to ixl.req[idx]);
8         c.create(interface from ixl.ma[idx] to tr[idx].ma);
9 end scenario

```

Parameter *idx* specifies the index to be used to register the new train in the collaboration’s array *c.tr*[·] of references to existing trains. Parameter *c* references the collaboration where the train should be registered. Parameter *b* specifies the segment where the train is supposed to enter; this may only occur on segments b10 or b14. Parameter *rmgr* references the route manager who indicates in its Boolean array parameter *createTrainCnd*[*idx*] whether the train can be created.

An instance of the elementary scenario becomes active as soon as (1) an admissible segment *b* is referenced, and (2) the segment is empty, and (3) the route manager’s create-train-condition at index *idx* becomes true. This is specified in the precondition.

When the scenario instance becomes active, its initial action is immediately performed: (1) The auxiliary frame-variable is initialised to the empty set. This means that the LTL specification can only become true if the referenced objects set their parameters correspondingly. It is not allowed for the *IncomingTrain* instance to write to any object parameters. Here, this implies that segment *b* needs to detect itself that a train has entered the segment.

The LTL formula specifies that in the next state after the scenario has become active, the segment *b* must have registered that it is being occupied, and the segment’s track vacancy detector must have set the occupied-flag to true. In the following state the scenario execution is no longer active.

The utilisation of the frame-variables allows to easily specify test oracles or test stimulators, or combinations thereof: A scenario instance acting as stimulator may change object parameters contained in the frame in order to ensure that the specification formula continuously evaluates to true. Instances of the *IncomingTrain*() scenario type, however, act as test oracles: Since the frame-variable is empty, a scenario instance can never change any object parameters to ensure that the LTL specification evaluates to true. In this case, if track element *b* fails

to set its occupied flag, the LTL specification $\mathbf{X}(b.occ \wedge \dots)$ is violated, and the test fails. The verdict variable is set automatically to `verdict = fail` by the SCSL execution environment.

The initial action uses collaboration c 's method `create()` to create a train that is registered in $c.tr[idx]$ and initialised with segment b as train position and current MA. Parameter setting $req = 0$ means that no new MA is currently requested. The new train is wired to the IXL by creating interfaces from the train's req parameter to the IXL's request array at index idx and from the IXL's ma -array at index idx to the train's ma -parameter.

MA Request. The following elementary scenario type specifies how the request of MAs is performed by a train identified by index idx and stored in collaboration c in array element $c.tr[idx]$. Parameter r specifies the id of the route to be requested. The route manager is needed to decide about when to trigger the request for MA.

Listing 7: Scenario type for acquiring movement authority.

```

1 elementary scenario RequestMA( idx : TrainId, c : collaboration, r : RouteId, rmgr :
   RouteMgr )
2 precondition
   c.tr[idx] ≠ null ∧ tr[idx].ma = ixlTbl[r].from ∧ rmgr.maReqCnd[idx]
3 spec (c.tr[idx].req = r) U (c.tr[idx].req = r ∧ c.tr[idx].ma = ixlTbl[r].to ∧
4   r ∈ rmgr.ar ∧ X c.tr[idx].req = 0 ∧ XX¬active)
5 initact frame := {c.tr[idx].req, rmgr.ar};
6 end scenario

```

A runnable elementary scenario instance of `RequestMA()` can become active if the referenced train exists in the collaboration and its current MA ranges up to the start of the route r that is requested. This restriction is motivated by the fact that trains should not request MAs for routes that are still too far away, so that the MA request would unnecessarily block other trains from allocating this route. Therefore, trains may only request route allocations for a subsequent route, directly following the route it is currently travelling on. To test IXL capabilities like sequential release, it is useful to have an even more refined precondition for `RequestMA()`-instances: To this end, the route manager provides a Boolean array that contains a flag when the train with index idx may issue its MA request.

The scenario specification states that at the start of the MA request, the train's route request must be set to route id r . Here, $c.tr[idx].req$ is in the frame of the scenario instance. This means that the instance “forces” the train to issue the route request. If a system test runs as a software simulation, the scenario instance sends a command message to the train instance which then sets its request parameter to r . For a real-world system test, the scenario instance would send a command to the train engine driver to perform the MA request. These test implementation aspects are abstracted away in the scenario specification by simply stating that the scenario instance forces the train's request parameter to assume value r .

After issuing the request for route r , this request remains active until the train's MA is set to the last element of the requested route r . The train's MA is set by the IXL which has an output interface from its parameter $ixl.ma[idx]$ to train parameter $c.tr[idx].ma$. This is shown in the collaboration specification presented in Section 5.1. Next, the request is reset to zero (“no request”), and after that the scenario instance terminates.

Route Traversal. The following elementary scenario type specifies how trains tr traverse an allocated route consisting of track elements s .

Listing 8: Scenario type for traversing a locked route.

```

1 elementary scenario Traverse(  $tr : \mathbf{Train}$ ,  $s : \mathbf{ElementId}^*$  )
2   precondition  $tr \neq \mathbf{null} \wedge tr.pos = hd(s) \wedge tr.ma = last(s)$ 
3   spec  $\bigwedge_e \text{in } b \neg e.occ$ 
4   spec  $\mathbf{G}(tr.pos = last(a) \vee (b \neq \varepsilon \wedge tr.pos = hd(b)))$ 
5   spec  $\mathbf{F}(last(a) = last(s) \wedge \neg last(front(a)).occ \wedge \mathbf{X}\neg active)$ 
6   initact frame :=  $\emptyset$ ;  $a := \langle hd(s) \rangle$ ;  $b := tl(s)$ ;
7   cndact when (  $b \neq \varepsilon \wedge hd(b).occ$  ) /  $a := a.hd(b)$ ;  $b := tl(b)$ ;
8 end scenario
```

The precondition for commencing the traversal is that the train resides on the route's initial element and has an MA to its last element. Two auxiliary variables a, b typed as sequences of track element identifiers are introduced. Sequence a contains the route's elements that have already been traversed by the train, or where the train is currently residing on. Sequence b contains the elements still to be traversed by the train. The the init action and the condition/action specifications (lines 6,7) control the updates of a and b : As soon as the head of b becomes occupied, this means that the train has entered $hd(b)$. Therefore, $hd(b)$ is appended to a and removed from b .

The first specification (line 3) states the safety condition that initially all elements in front of the train until the end of the route are vacant. During route traversal, the head of the train always resides in $last(a)$ or $hd(b)$. This is stated in the specification in line 4. The invariant $a.b = s$ is preserved throughout the execution of this scenario. The third LTL specification (line 5) states that the train will finally reach and be completely contained in the last segment of the route, after which the scenario execution terminates.⁹

Note. Since for any track element e , the occupation indication $e.occ$ is anonymous (vacancy detectors), we rely on a route-locking safety property to ensure that any occupancy observed on elements of s during traversal can only stem from tr . This safety property is expressed in the test-specific scenarios introduced in Section 4.

⁹ Note that $\neg last(front(a)).occ$ states that the last but one element of a is empty, so that the train is completely contained in $last(a)$.

Trains Without MA don't Move. The following elementary scenario type specifies the safety condition that trains tr without MA remain in their current position.

Listing 9: Scenario type for traversing a locked route.

```

1 elementary scenario StopWithoutMA(  $tr : \text{Train}$  )
2   precondition  $tr \neq \text{null}$ 
3   spec  $\mathbf{G}(tr.pos = currentMA \Rightarrow \mathbf{X}(tr.pos = currentMA \vee tr.ma \neq currentMA))$ 
4   initact frame :=  $\emptyset$ ;  $currentMA := tr.ma$ 
5   cndact when (  $tr.ma \neq currentMA$  )/ $currentMA := tr.ma$ 
6 end scenario
```

The LTL specification states that either the train's position remains at its current MA represented by auxiliary variable $currentMA$ or that the train position is not (yet) at the current MA. Auxiliary variable $currentMA$ always contains the train's actual MA value. To understand this interaction between LTL specification and condition/action specification, it is important to note that changes made in an action become visible in the *next* execution cycle of an elementary scenario instance. Therefore, clause $tr.ma \neq currentMA$ means that the train's MA has just changed but not yet become visible in $currentMA$. In the next execution cycle, $tr.ma = currentMA$ will hold again.

Resolve a locked train route of some train tr . This scenario type specifies how routes that are no longer occupied by any train are no longer marked as occupied in the route manager.

Listing 10: Scenario type for resolving a locked route.

```

1 elementary scenario Resolve(  $tr : \text{Train}, r : \text{RouteId}, rmgr : \text{RouteMgr}$  )
2   precondition  $tr \neq \text{null} \wedge r \in rmgr.ar \wedge tr.ma = ixlTbl[r].to$ 
3   spec  $(r \in rmgr.ar) \mathbf{U}$ 
4      $(r \in rmgr.ar \wedge tr.pos = ixlTbl[r].to \wedge \neg last(front(ixlTbl[r].elems)).occ \wedge$ 
5        $\mathbf{X}r \notin rmgr.ar \wedge \mathbf{XX}\neg active)$ 
6   initact frame :=  $\{rmgr.ar\}$ ;
7 end scenario
```

The precondition states that the route is currently marked as occupied in the route manager and that the train has MA until the end of this route. The specification states that the route remains registered in $rmgr.ar$ up to and including the point in time where the train has reached the end of the route and is completely contained in the route's last segment, so that the last but one segment is empty. Then the route id is removed from the route manager's set of allocated routes, and the scenario execution terminates.

Outgoing Trains. The effect of trains tr leaving the railway network is specified by the following elementary scenario type. Segment $s \in \{\mathbf{t10}, \mathbf{t14}\}$ is the last segment *inside* the railway network. Segment $b \in \{\mathbf{b10}, \mathbf{b14}\}$ is one of the exit segments.

Listing 11: Scenario type for trains leaving the station area.

```

1 elementary scenario OutgoingTrain( tr : Train, c : collaboration,
2                                     s : Segment, b : Segment )
3   precondition
4      $tr \neq \text{null} \wedge tr.pos = s \wedge ((s = \mathbf{t10} \wedge b = \mathbf{b10}) \vee (s = \mathbf{t14} \wedge b = \mathbf{b14})) \wedge \neg b.occ$ 
5   initact frame :=  $\emptyset$ ;
6   cndact when (  $\neg s.occ \wedge tr.pos = b$  ) / c.delete(tr);
7 end scenario

```

Runnable instances of this scenario start their execution when the train has entered s ; the associated exit segment must be unoccupied. Segments s and b must be adjacent to each other. As soon as the train has exited segment s and resides on b , the train is removed from the collaboration c by invoking its `delete()` function. This has the effect that the train reference is set to `null` at its position in the $c.tr[\cdot]$ -array and that all interfaces referring to train tr are removed from the collaboration.

Coverage Observer. This elementary scenario type (Listing 12) acts as an observer: it does not interfere with the test execution but monitors relevant information which is test coverage-related for the scenario specified here. For the test objectives identified in Section 1, coverage is measured by the routes that have been traversed, the conflicts that have been checked, and the different sequences in which routes have been allocated to trains. Coverage is recorded by the observer in the global data structure $C = (N, E, c_N, cl_E, c_E)$ introduced in Section 3.1.

Listing 12: Scenario type for the coverage observer.

```

1 elementary scenario CoverageObserver( ixl : Ixl, rmgr : RouteMgr )
2 spec  $\mathbf{G}(\text{verdict} \neq \text{pass} \Rightarrow (\mathbf{X} C = (N, E, c_N, cl_E, c_E)))$ 
3 spec  $\mathbf{G}(\text{verdict} = \text{pass} \Rightarrow (\mathbf{X} C = (N', E', c'_N, cl'_E, c'_E) \wedge \mathbf{XX}\neg\text{active}))$ 
4
5 initact  $(N', E', c'_N, cl'_E, c'_E) := (N, E, c_N, cl_E, c_E);$ 
6    $E_{2,3} := \{(r, r') \in E \mid cl_E(r, r') \in \{2, 3\}\};$ 
7    $E_4 := \{(r, r') \in E \mid cl_E(r, r') = 4\};$ 
8   frame :=  $\{N, E, c_N, cl_E, c_E\};$ 
9
10 for  $r \in N$  do
11   cndact when (  $\neg c'_N(r) \wedge r \in rmgr.ar$  ) /  $c'_N := c'_N \oplus \{r \mapsto \text{true}\};$ 
12 endfor
13
14 for  $(r_1, r_2) \in E_{2,3}$  do
15   cndact when (  $\neg c'_E(r_1, r_2) \wedge r_1 \in rmgr.ar \wedge (\bigvee_{i \in \text{TrainId}} ixl.req[i] = r_2)$  ) /
16      $c'_E := c'_E \oplus \{(r_1, r_2) \mapsto \text{true}\};$ 
17 endfor
18
19 for  $(r_1, r_2) \in E_4$  do
20   cndact when (  $\neg c'_E(r_1, r_2) \wedge (\bigvee_{i \neq j \in \text{TrainId}} ixl.req[i] = r_1 \wedge ixl.req[j] = r_2)$  ) /

```

```

21          $c'_E := c'_E \oplus \{(r_1, r_2) \mapsto \mathbf{true}\};$ 
22     endfor
23 end scenario

```

Initially (line 5), instances of *CoverageObserver()* copy the components of the coverage graph C to auxiliary variables. Only if the test execution terminates with verdict **pass**, the updates made on these auxiliary variables are copied back to C , whereupon the scenario terminates. This is specified in line 3. Thus, coverage marks collected during a failing test execution remain tentative and are not committed to the persistent coverage graph.

The initial action also creates two set-valued auxiliary variables $E_{2,3}$ and E_4 . The former contains all graph edges to be covered in conflict tests or sequencing tests ($cl_E(r, r') \in \{2, 3\}$), the latter all edges associated with robustness tests.

The updates of all graph-related auxiliary variables are performed in condition/action statements. The first for-loop containing these statements is indexed over all routes r (i.e. nodes $r \in N$). When $c'_N(r)$ is still **false** and the Boolean expression $r \in rmgr.ar$ changes from **false** to **true**, then action $c'_N := c'_N \oplus \{r \mapsto \mathbf{true}\}$ is executed. Symbol “ \oplus ” denotes *functional overriding*: $c'_N \oplus \{r \mapsto \mathbf{true}\}$ is the function that maps r to **true** and all other arguments $r' \neq r$ to $c'_N(r')$.

The second for-loop is indexed over all pairs (r_1, r_2) associated with test classes 2 and 3. Each change condition specified there triggers the action whenever $c'_E(r_1, r_2)$ is still **false** and r_1 is already allocated, and at the same time a train requests route r_2 at the IXL.¹⁰ The action marks (r_1, r_2) as covered in function c'_E .

The third for-loop runs over all pairs (r_1, r_2) associated with robustness tests (Class 4). The actions are triggered when $c'_E(r_1, r_2)$ is still **false** and two different trains request r_1 and r_2 , respectively. Recall that these requests can never be granted, since this would lead to head-on collisions. Since these requests must not be granted, the associated elementary scenario instances are expected to observe that no MA is issued. The test fails if one or both MAs are granted.

The responsibilities of the coverage observer are intentionally separated from the responsibilities of the test-specific scenario instances. The observer does not check whether the IXL reaction to a covered situation is correct; it only records that the coverage condition associated with a node or edge of C has been triggered. Correctness of the IXL reaction is checked by the test-specific oracle clauses, for example those ensuring that conflicting routes are respected, points are set appropriately, and MAs are granted only for requested routes whose elements are unoccupied. Moreover, the elementary scenario instances such as *Traverse()* and *OutgoingTrain()* ensure that the test execution progresses to the intended final state. Consequently, an edge or node is considered successfully cov-

¹⁰ Note that the train $tr[i]$ issuing request $ixl.req[i] = r_2$ is necessarily distinct from the train $tr[j]$ possessing MA for route r_1 since $tr[j]$ switches its request back to zero as soon as the MA for r_1 has been obtained. After that, $tr[j]$ may request new MAs, but never for routes that are in conflict with route r_1 it is currently traversing.

ered only in conjunction with a system test execution that terminates without violation of its test-specific oracles.

4 Templates for Test-Specific Elementary Scenarios

Recall from Section 1.3 that four test classes have been identified that should be covered in a comprehensive system test suite. We introduce elementary scenario type templates for each of these classes.

4.1 Template for Class 1: Route Allocation Tests

Route allocation tests check whether all specified routes can be correctly allocated and are properly released after traversal. The safety and correctness conditions for route allocation are specified by the scenario template displayed in Listing 13.

Listing 13: Template for scenario checking route allocations – test class 1.

```

1 elementary scenario <SYSTEST NAME>( ixl : Ixl, rmgr : RouteMgr )
2
3 spec G (|rmgr.ar| ≤ 1)
4
5 spec G ( ( ixl.ma[0] = <ENTRYSEG> ∧ Xixl.ma[0] = <REND> ) ⇒
6           ( ixl.req[0] = <ROUTE ID> ∧
7             ixl.ptCmd[<POINT>] = <POINTSTATE> ∧
8             ixl.ptSts[<POINT>] = ixl.ptCmd[<POINT>] ∧
9             <LIST OF><UNOCCUPIED ELEMENT><END LIST> ∧
10            X(<ROUTE ID> ∈ rmgr.ar) ) )
11
12 spec G ( ( ixl.ma[0] = <SEG> ∧ Xixl.ma[0] = <REND> ) ⇒
13           ( ixl.req[0] = <ROUTE ID> ∧
14             ixl.ptCmd[<POINT>] = <POINTSTATE> ∧
15             ixl.ptSts[<POINT>] = ixl.ptCmd[<POINT>] ∧
16             <LIST OF><UNOCCUPIED ELEMENT><END LIST> ∧
17            X(<ROUTE ID> ∈ rmgr.ar) ) )
18
19 spec G ( ( ixl.ma[0] = <SEG> ∧ Xixl.ma[0] = <EXITSEG> ) ⇒
20           ( ixl.req[0] = <ROUTE ID> ∧ ¬ixl.occ[<EXITSEG>] ∧
21             X(<ROUTE ID> ∈ rmgr.ar ∧
22             F(¬ixl.occ[<SEG>] ∧ ¬ixl.occ[<EXITSEG>] ∧
23             Xrmgr.ar = ∅ ∧ XX EoT))) )
24
25 initact frame := ∅;
26 end scenario

```

All templates presented in this paper are instantiated by replacing template parameters `<parameter-name>` by concrete values or expressions and keeping the syntactic elements without template parameters unchanged. In most cases, the modification consists of replacing template parameters by concrete values. The `<LIST OF>` template directive indicates that a list of the subsequent template text should be produced. List specifications can be nested and are terminated by the `<END LIST>` token. A few template parameters are handled like production rules in a syntax specification: They are replaced by expressions that are explained in the associated template instantiation rules. In the template discussed here, `<UNOCCUPIED ELEMENT>` represents such a production rule.

The instantiation rules for the scenario template above are as follows.

1. All scenarios of Class 1 involve a single train only. This train carries index zero (see explanation of collaborations in Section 5.1).
2. The second specification handles the entry of the train into the track network. The train’s entry segment for visiting the network is denoted by `<ENTRYSEG>` and must be one of the segments `b10` or `b14`. Template parameter `<REND>` denotes the last segment of the first route to be allocated by the train. This route must start at the entry segment: For entry segment `b10`, for example, routes 1 or 3 can be used, so `<REND>` equals `t12` or `t20`. These route numbers are used for instantiating the `<ROUTE ID>` parameter. Parameter `<POINT>` denotes the point on the respective route. The points on a route are extracted from the IXL table, component `ixlTbl[<ROUTE ID>].pp`. For both routes 1 and 3, for example, this would be `t11`. Component `ixlTbl[<ROUTE ID>].pp` is also used to look up the required point positions; this would be, for example, `plus` for route 1 and `minus` for route 3. These position values are used when instantiating the `<POINTSTATE>` parameter. The list of unoccupied elements contains one entry for all track elements of the route but the first¹¹. The list entries are connected by the and operator ‘`^`’. Each list entry is of the form `¬ixl.occ[<ELEMENT>]`, where `<ELEMENT> ∈ ElementId` is instantiated to the respective track element on the route. For the example of route 1, the `<LIST OF><UNOCCUPIED ELEMENT><END LIST>` expression is instantiated to

$$\neg ixl.occ[t10] \wedge \neg ixl.occ[t11] \wedge \neg ixl.occ[t12].$$

3. The third specification describes the allocation of the middle route, located between the initial route and the exit route. Template parameter `<SEG>` always refers to a segment *inside* the railway network. The last element of the initial route – this is stored in `ixl.ma[0]` while the train has MA for the first route only – must coincide with the first element of the middle route, and the last element of the middle route (represented by template parameter `<REND>`) needs to be the same as the first element of the exit route. This results in the following possible sequences of routes, as can be extracted from `ixlTbl`: (a) routes 1.2.9, (b) routes 3.4.9, (c) routes 5.6.10, and (d) routes 7.8.10. The template parameters and their instantiation rules are the same as described in the previous rule.

¹¹ Since the train is already residing on the first element, this can never be unoccupied)

4. The fourth specification block specifies the expected behaviour when the train exits the network. The `<EXITSEG>` must be `b14` if the entry segment was `b10` and vice versa. The segment template parameter `<SEG>` must be instantiated to a segment connecting directly to the exit segment, so it is instantiated to `t14` if the exit segment is `b14` and to `t10` if the exit segment is `b10`. Parameter `<ROUTE ID>` is instantiated to the exit route id: this is route number 9 for exit via `t14.b14` and number 10 for exit via `t10.b10`.

4.2 Templates for Class 2: Conflict Tests

Conflicts between trains competing for MAs can arise in two fundamentally different ways: (1) temporal blocking between succeeding trains on the same route sequence, and (2) resource conflicts between trains requesting overlapping routes. This leads to the introduction of two sub-classes of conflict tests.

Succeeding train conflict. If tr_0 is ahead of tr_1 on the same route sequence, tr_1 can only obtain movement authority for a route in this sequence once tr_0 has vacated this route completely, including the overlapping boundary element between this route and the next. More formally, suppose that trains tr_0 and tr_1 traverse the same sequence $r_1.r_2.r_3 \dots$ of consecutive routes, and tr_0 is the leading train. If tr_0 currently traverses route r_i , then tr_1 (a) can only get an MA for route r_{i-1} if tr_0 has already left the first element of r_i , since this element coincides with the last element of r_{i-1} , and (b) tr_1 can only get an MA for r_i after tr_0 has left r_i completely. Another variant of succeeding train conflicts (not considered for testing in this paper) is that train tr_1 follows tr_0 on a route r_2 that shares a prefix of the track element sequence that tr_0 has allocated. An example would be route 1 allocated for train tr_0 while tr_1 tries to obtain an MA for route 3.

Conflicting routes. Suppose trains tr_0 and tr_1 plan to traverse two different routes r_0 and r_1 , respectively. Suppose further that tr_0 already has MA for r_0 . If r_0 and r_1 are in conflict (i.e. they share one or more track elements), tr_1 can only get an MA for r_1 after tr_0 has completely traversed the conflicting track elements.

The different nature of these two cases suggests to structure Class 2 tests into two sub-classes, each with its own templates for an elementary scenario type controlling the test execution.

Class 2.1: Succeeding Train Tests. In Listing 14, the template for conducting succeeding train tests is shown. All tests involve two trains that are identified with indexes zero and one inside the template. Both trains start at the same entry element (`b10` or `b14`) and finally leave at the opposite exit element. Train 0 is always the first to enter the network, train 1 follows. To cross the network, they have to traverse the same three consecutive routes that are represented by template parameters `<R1>`, `<R2>`, `<R3>`. For the instantiation of these route parameters, the following additional rules apply.

1. Route $\langle R1 \rangle$ must be one of the entry routes 1, 3 or 5, 7 specified in the IXL Table 1.
2. In the cases of entry routes 1, 3, route $\langle R3 \rangle$ must be the exit route 9, in the cases of entry routes 5, 7, it must be the exit route 10.
3. Route $\langle R2 \rangle$ must be the uniquely determined route whose first element coincides with the last element of $\langle R1 \rangle$ and whose last element coincides with the first element of $\langle R3 \rangle$. More formally,

$$ixlTbl[\langle R2 \rangle].from = ixlTbl[\langle R1 \rangle].to \wedge ixlTbl[\langle R2 \rangle].to = ixlTbl[\langle R3 \rangle].from.$$

The purpose of succeeding train tests is to ensure that the second train can only obtain movement authorities when the leading train has sufficiently cleared the shared boundary elements between consecutive routes.

The LTL specification in line 4 states that no other routes than $\langle R1 \rangle, \langle R2 \rangle, \langle R3 \rangle$ may be allocated at any time. The subsequent LTL specifications each state the safety conditions to hold for one train obtaining MA for one route: In lines 6 to 12, for example, the LTL specification states that if train 0's MA changes from the start of route $\langle R1 \rangle$ to the end of route $\langle R1 \rangle$ the following conditions must hold: (a) Train must have requested MA for route $\langle R1 \rangle$. (b) The point in route $\langle R1 \rangle$ must be in the required point state for this route, and it must have been commanded by the IXL: Template parameter $\langle POINT1 \rangle$ is instantiated by the identifier of the point associated with route $\langle R1 \rangle$; both point id and required point state can be obtained from the **pp**-component of the IXL Table 1. (c) All elements of route $\langle R1 \rangle$ but the first must be unoccupied. This is specified by the template list parameter $\langle LIST\ OF \rangle \langle UNOCCUPIED\ ELEMENT1 \rangle \langle END\ LIST \rangle$, as has already been explained above for Listing 13. The remaining specifications are analogous for routes $\langle R2 \rangle, \langle R3 \rangle$ and for train 1.

Listing 14: Template for the elementary scenario to be used for succeeding train tests (Class 2.1).

```

1 elementary scenario <SYSTEST NAME>
2     (ixl : Ixl, rmgr : RouteMgr)
3
4 spec G (rmgr.ar  $\subseteq$  {<R1>, <R2>, <R3>})
5
6 spec G ( (ixl.ma[0] = ixlTbl[<R1>].from  $\wedge$ 
7           Xixl.ma[0] = ixlTbl[<R1>].to)  $\Rightarrow$ 
8           (ixl.req[0] = <R1>  $\wedge$ 
9             ixl.ptCmd[<POINT1>] = <POINTSTATE1>  $\wedge$ 
10            ixl.ptSts[<POINT1>] = ixl.ptCmd[<POINT1>]  $\wedge$ 
11            <LIST OF><UNOCCUPIED ELEMENT1><END LIST>  $\wedge$ 
12            X(rmgr.ar = {<R1>})))
13
14 spec G ( (ixl.ma[0] = ixlTbl[<R2>].from  $\wedge$ 
15           Xixl.ma[0] = ixlTbl[<R2>].to)  $\Rightarrow$ 
16           (ixl.req[0] = <R2>  $\wedge$ 

```

```

17      $ixl.ptCmd[\langle \text{POINT2} \rangle] = \langle \text{POINTSTATE2} \rangle \wedge$ 
18      $ixl.ptSts[\langle \text{POINT2} \rangle] = ixl.ptCmd[\langle \text{POINT2} \rangle] \wedge$ 
19      $\langle \text{LIST OF} \rangle \langle \text{UNOCCUPIED ELEMENT2} \rangle \langle \text{END LIST} \rangle \wedge$ 
20      $\mathbf{X}(\langle \text{R2} \rangle \in rmgr.ar))$ 
21
22 spec G  $((ixl.ma[0] = ixlTbl[\langle \text{R3} \rangle].from \wedge$ 
23      $\mathbf{X}ixl.ma[0] = ixlTbl[\langle \text{R3} \rangle].to) \Rightarrow$ 
24      $(ixl.req[0] = \langle \text{R3} \rangle \wedge$ 
25      $ixl.ptCmd[\langle \text{POINT3} \rangle] = \langle \text{POINTSTATE3} \rangle \wedge$ 
26      $ixl.ptSts[\langle \text{POINT3} \rangle] = ixl.ptCmd[\langle \text{POINT3} \rangle] \wedge$ 
27      $\langle \text{LIST OF} \rangle \langle \text{UNOCCUPIED ELEMENT3} \rangle \langle \text{END LIST} \rangle \wedge$ 
28      $\mathbf{X}(\langle \text{R3} \rangle \in rmgr.ar))$ )
29
30 spec G  $((ixl.ma[1] = ixlTbl[\langle \text{R1} \rangle].from \wedge$ 
31      $\mathbf{X}ixl.ma[1] = ixlTbl[\langle \text{R1} \rangle].to) \Rightarrow$ 
32      $(ixl.req[1] = \langle \text{R1} \rangle \wedge$ 
33      $ixl.ptCmd[\langle \text{POINT1} \rangle] = \langle \text{POINTSTATE1} \rangle \wedge$ 
34      $ixl.ptSts[\langle \text{POINT1} \rangle] = ixl.ptCmd[\langle \text{POINT1} \rangle] \wedge$ 
35      $\langle \text{LIST OF} \rangle \langle \text{UNOCCUPIED ELEMENT1} \rangle \langle \text{END LIST} \rangle \wedge$ 
36      $\mathbf{X}(\langle \text{R1} \rangle \in rmgr.ar))$ )
37
38 spec G  $((ixl.ma[1] = ixlTbl[\langle \text{R2} \rangle].from \wedge$ 
39      $\mathbf{X}ixl.ma[1] = ixlTbl[\langle \text{R2} \rangle].to) \Rightarrow$ 
40      $(ixl.req[1] = \langle \text{R2} \rangle \wedge$ 
41      $ixl.ptCmd[\langle \text{POINT2} \rangle] = \langle \text{POINTSTATE2} \rangle \wedge$ 
42      $ixl.ptSts[\langle \text{POINT2} \rangle] = ixl.ptCmd[\langle \text{POINT2} \rangle] \wedge$ 
43      $\langle \text{LIST OF} \rangle \langle \text{UNOCCUPIED ELEMENT2} \rangle \langle \text{END LIST} \rangle \wedge$ 
44      $\mathbf{X}(\langle \text{R2} \rangle \in rmgr.ar))$ )
45
46 spec G  $((ixl.ma[1] = ixlTbl[\langle \text{R3} \rangle].from \wedge$ 
47      $\mathbf{X}ixl.ma[1] = ixlTbl[\langle \text{R3} \rangle].to) \Rightarrow$ 
48      $(ixl.req[1] = \langle \text{R3} \rangle \wedge$ 
49      $ixl.ptCmd[\langle \text{POINT3} \rangle] = \langle \text{POINTSTATE3} \rangle \wedge$ 
50      $ixl.ptSts[\langle \text{POINT3} \rangle] = ixl.ptCmd[\langle \text{POINT3} \rangle] \wedge$ 
51      $\langle \text{LIST OF} \rangle \langle \text{UNOCCUPIED ELEMENT3} \rangle \langle \text{END LIST} \rangle \wedge$ 
52      $\mathbf{X}(\langle \text{R3} \rangle \in rmgr.ar \wedge \mathbf{F}(rmgr.ar = \emptyset \wedge \mathbf{X} \text{ EoT}))$ )
53
54 initact frame :=  $\emptyset$ ;
55 end scenario

```

Class 2.2: Conflicting Routes Tests. The following scenarios check that conflicting routes are allocated safely. In Class 2.2 tests, trains do not necessarily traverse the whole network. Instead, they may allocate and traverse just one

route that conflicts with that of another train. Consequently, some trains already reside inside the network at start-of-test, and some trains remain inside at end-of-test.

Applying a pairwise testing heuristic to the route-conflict relation of the interlocking table, Class 2.2 aims at covering every admissible pair of conflicting routes at least once. Route pairs representing succeeding-train situations are covered by Class 2.1 and its extension for succeeding trains with diverging follow-up routes. Route pairs like (1, 5), (1, 6), (1, 10) that can only be exercised from operationally unwanted deadlock-prone configurations are assigned to robustness testing. The remaining normal behaviour route conflicts can be covered by only four system tests that are listed in Table 2: two three-train tests, each covering two pairs of conflicting routes and two two-train tests, each covering one pair of conflicting routes.

Table 2: Selected train placements and route specifications for Class 2.2 route-conflict coverage.

	Tr0		Tr1		Tr2		Covered conflicts
No.	elem	rMA (dir)	elem	rMA (dir)	elem	rMA (dir)	
1	b10	1;2 (UP)	t20	8 (DOWN)	b14	7 (DOWN)	(1, 8), (2, 7)
2	b10	3;4 (UP)	t12	6 (DOWN)	b14	5 (DOWN)	(3, 6), (4, 5)
3	t12	2;9 (UP)	t20	4;9 (UP)	—	—	(2, 4)
4	t12	6;10 (DOWN)	t20	8;10 (DOWN)	—	—	(6, 8)

rMA: requested movement authority for route.

elem: initial placement of train.

Although test cases 1,2 and 3,4 instantiate the same underlying coverage criterion, we use separate elementary scenario templates for three-train and two-train placements. This keeps the scenario specifications compact and avoids optional parameters or conditional branches that would obscure the intended test behaviour. The distinction is therefore not semantic, but pragmatic: it preserves the readability advantage of scenario-based test specifications over monolithic MBT models. Since the template instantiation is performed automatically by the GPT, two templates instead of one do not create any manual overhead.

The scenario template in Listing 15 handles the three-train tests, and the scenario template in Listing 16 the two-train tests.

Listing 15: Template for elementary scenario used in three-train conflict tests. (Class 2.2).

```
1 elementary scenario <SYSTEST NAME>
```

2 (*ixl* : *Ix1*, *rmgr* : *RouteMgr*)

3

4 **precondition** $\langle R3 \rangle \in ixlTbl[\langle R1 \rangle].conf \wedge \langle R4 \rangle \in ixlTbl[\langle R2 \rangle].conf;$

5

6 **spec** $\mathbf{G}(rmgr.ar \subseteq \{\langle R1 \rangle, \langle R2 \rangle, \langle R3 \rangle, \langle R4 \rangle\} \wedge$

7 $\neg(\{\langle R1 \rangle, \langle R3 \rangle\} \subseteq rmgr.ar) \wedge \neg(\{\langle R2 \rangle, \langle R4 \rangle\} \subseteq rmgr.ar))$

8

9 **spec** $rmgr.maReqCnd[0] \mathbf{U}$

10 $(ixl.req[0] = \langle R1 \rangle \wedge \neg rmgr.maReqCnd[0] \wedge$

11 $(\neg rmgr.maReqCnd[0]) \mathbf{U} (\langle R4 \rangle \in rmgr.ar \wedge \mathbf{G}rmgr.maReqCnd[0]))$

12

13 **spec** $(\neg rmgr.maReqCnd[1]) \mathbf{U} (\langle R1 \rangle \in rmgr.ar \wedge \mathbf{G}rmgr.maReqCnd[1])$

14

15 **spec** $\mathbf{G}((ixl.ma[0] = ixlTbl[\langle R1 \rangle].from \wedge$

16 $\mathbf{X}ixl.ma[0] = ixlTbl[\langle R1 \rangle].to) \Rightarrow$

17 $(ixl.req[0] = \langle R1 \rangle \wedge$

18 $ixl.ptCmd[\langle POINT1 \rangle] = \langle POINTSTATE1 \rangle \wedge$

19 $ixl.ptSts[\langle POINT1 \rangle] = ixl.ptCmd[\langle POINT1 \rangle] \wedge$

20 $\langle LIST\ OF \rangle \langle UNOCCUPIED\ ELEMENT1 \rangle \langle END\ LIST \rangle \wedge$

21 $\mathbf{X}(\langle R1 \rangle \in rmgr.ar))$

22

23 **spec** $\mathbf{G}((ixl.ma[0] = ixlTbl[\langle R2 \rangle].from \wedge$

24 $\mathbf{X}ixl.ma[0] = ixlTbl[\langle R2 \rangle].to) \Rightarrow$

25 $(ixl.req[0] = \langle R2 \rangle \wedge$

26 $ixl.ptCmd[\langle POINT2 \rangle] = \langle POINTSTATE2 \rangle \wedge$

27 $ixl.ptSts[\langle POINT2 \rangle] = ixl.ptCmd[\langle POINT2 \rangle] \wedge$

28 $\langle LIST\ OF \rangle \langle UNOCCUPIED\ ELEMENT2 \rangle \langle END\ LIST \rangle \wedge$

29 $\mathbf{X}(\langle R2 \rangle \in rmgr.ar))$

30

31 **spec** $\mathbf{G}((ixl.ma[1] = ixlTbl[\langle R3 \rangle].from \wedge$

32 $\mathbf{X}ixl.ma[1] = ixlTbl[\langle R3 \rangle].to) \Rightarrow$

33 $(ixl.req[1] = \langle R3 \rangle \wedge$

34 $ixl.ptCmd[\langle POINT3 \rangle] = \langle POINTSTATE3 \rangle \wedge$

35 $ixl.ptSts[\langle POINT3 \rangle] = ixl.ptCmd[\langle POINT3 \rangle] \wedge$

36 $\langle LIST\ OF \rangle \langle UNOCCUPIED\ ELEMENT3 \rangle \langle END\ LIST \rangle \wedge$

37 $\mathbf{X}(\langle R3 \rangle \in rmgr.ar))$

38

39 **spec** $\mathbf{G}((ixl.ma[2] = ixlTbl[\langle R4 \rangle].from \wedge$

40 $\mathbf{X}ixl.ma[2] = ixlTbl[\langle R4 \rangle].to) \Rightarrow$

41 $(ixl.req[2] = \langle R4 \rangle \wedge$

42 $ixl.ptCmd[\langle POINT4 \rangle] = \langle POINTSTATE4 \rangle \wedge$

43 $ixl.ptSts[\langle POINT4 \rangle] = ixl.ptCmd[\langle POINT4 \rangle] \wedge$

44 $\langle LIST\ OF \rangle \langle UNOCCUPIED\ ELEMENT4 \rangle \langle END\ LIST \rangle \wedge$

45 $\mathbf{X}(\langle R4 \rangle \in rmgr.ar))$

```

46
47 spec  $\mathbf{G}(\langle \mathbf{R2} \rangle \in rmgr.ar \wedge \mathbf{X}(\langle \mathbf{R2} \rangle \notin rmgr.ar) \Rightarrow \mathbf{XX} \text{ EoT})$ 
48
49 initact frame := {rmgr.maReqCnd[0], rmgr.maReqCnd[1]};
50 end scenario

```

The template parameters for the elementary scenario template shown in Listing 15 have the following instantiation rules.

1. In each of these instantiations, four routes are involved, and the generic route parameters must be instantiated in such a way that $\langle \mathbf{R1} \rangle$ and $\langle \mathbf{R3} \rangle$ are in conflict with each other and $\langle \mathbf{R2} \rangle$ and $\langle \mathbf{R4} \rangle$ are in conflict as well. This is achieved by setting
 - $\langle \mathbf{R1} \rangle$ to the first route number listed in column $\text{Tr0.rMA}(\text{dir})$ of Table 2,
 - $\langle \mathbf{R2} \rangle$ to the second route number listed in column $\text{Tr0.rMA}(\text{dir})$ of Table 2,
 - $\langle \mathbf{R3} \rangle$ to the route number listed in column $\text{Tr1.rMA}(\text{dir})$ of Table 2, and
 - $\langle \mathbf{R4} \rangle$ to the route number listed in column $\text{Tr2.rMA}(\text{dir})$ of Table 2.
2. There are no generic parameters for trains: In all Class 2.2-tests with three trains, these have indexes 0,1,2 and train 0 traverses routes $\langle \mathbf{R1} \rangle$, $\langle \mathbf{R2} \rangle$, train 1 route $\langle \mathbf{R3} \rangle$, and train 2 route $\langle \mathbf{R4} \rangle$.
3. Template parameters $\langle \text{POINT}i \rangle$, $\langle \text{POINTSTATE}i \rangle$, and $\langle \text{LIST OF UNOCCUPIED ELEMENT}i \rangle \langle \text{END LIST} \rangle$ ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) are instantiated as already explained for Class 2.1 tests and the scenario template in Listing 14.

The behaviour of an elementary scenario type generated from the template in Listing 15 is as follows:

1. The precondition just states the requirements about routes being in conflict with each other.
2. The LTL specification in line 6 is the first safety condition to be monitored during test execution: none of the conflicting routes may be simultaneously allocated, and no other routes than $\langle \mathbf{R1} \rangle, \dots, \langle \mathbf{R4} \rangle$ must be allocated.
3. The specification in line 9 is the first of two constraints ensuring deadlock freedom: It states that train 0 may immediately request MA for its first route.¹² After that, however, it may only apply for an MA for the second route when train 2 has received MA for route $\langle \mathbf{R4} \rangle$ which is the case when $\langle \mathbf{R4} \rangle \in rmgr.ar$. From then on, requesting MAs is permanently enabled for train 0 ($\mathbf{G} rmgr.maReqCnd[0]$).
4. The second constraint ensuring deadlock freedom (line 13) ensures that train 1 will not request an MA before route $\langle \mathbf{R1} \rangle$ has been allocated. It is easy to check in the first two rows of Table 2 that this condition, together with the previous one, ensures deadlock freedom.

¹² Recall from Listing 7 that a request for MA will only be issued for train 0 if *rmgr.maReqCnd*[0] is **true**. By setting *rmgr.maReqCnd*[0] temporarily to **false**, a scenario instance created from the template in Listing 15 prevents train 0 from issuing a second MA request.

5. The LTL specification in line 15 states the safety conditions about point states and unoccupied track elements that must be fulfilled if route $\langle R1 \rangle$ is allocated to train 0. This follows exactly the same pattern as already explained for Class 2.1 tests and Listing 14.
6. The LTL specifications in lines 23, 31, and 39 state the analogous constraints for other routes and trains 0,1,2.
7. The specification in line 47 states the termination condition: an elementary scenario instantiated from this template terminates after route $\langle R2 \rangle$ has been released. In the tests involving three trains, route $\langle R2 \rangle$ is always the last to be released.

The Class 2.2 tests involving only two trains are specified by the template in Listing 16. For the two-train tests in rows 3 and 4 of Table 2, the route parameters are instantiated as follows. $\langle R1 \rangle$ is the first route listed in column $Tr0.rMA(dir)$, $\langle R2 \rangle$ is the second route listed in both columns $Tr0.rMA(dir)$ and $Tr1.rMA(dir)$, and $\langle R3 \rangle$ is the first route listed in column $Tr1.rMA(dir)$. Thus, row 3 instantiates $(\langle R1 \rangle, \langle R2 \rangle, \langle R3 \rangle) = (2,9,4)$, and row 4 instantiates $(\langle R1 \rangle, \langle R2 \rangle, \langle R3 \rangle) = (6,10,8)$.

The behaviour of scenario instances created from this template is as follows.

1. The two trains always start by trying to get MAs for two conflicting routes; then both trains try to leave the network via the same exit route.
2. The specification in line 5 states again that no other routes than $\langle R1 \rangle$, $\langle R2 \rangle$, $\langle R3 \rangle$ must be allocated and that conflicting routes must not be simultaneously allocated.
3. The specifications in lines 7, 15, 21, and 29 state the safety conditions that must hold when a route is allocated. For routes containing points, these include the required point commands and point states; in all cases, the relevant route elements ahead of the train must be unoccupied.
4. The termination condition in line 35 simply states that all track elements of the network, including entry/exit elements, must no longer be occupied. This indicates that both trains have left the network.
5. Note that no restrictions about when to issue requests for MA are specified: any sequence of MA allocation leads to both trains finally having left the network. Deadlocks are impossible in these tests.

Listing 16: Template for elementary scenario used in two-train conflict tests. (Class 2.2).

```

1 elementary scenario <SYSTEST NAME>( ixl : Ix1, rmgr : RouteMgr )
2
3 precondition <R3> ∈ ixlTbl[<R1>].conf;
4
5 spec G(rmgr.ar ⊆ {<R1>, <R2>, <R3>} ∧ ¬({<R1>, <R3>} ⊆ rmgr.ar))
6
7 spec G( ( ixl.ma[0] = ixlTbl[<R1>].from ∧
8           Xixl.ma[0] = ixlTbl[<R1>].to ) ⇒

```

```

9      (ixl.req[0] = <R1> ∧
10      ixl.ptCmd[<POINT1>] = <POINTSTATE1> ∧
11      ixl.ptSts[<POINT1>] = ixl.ptCmd[<POINT1>] ∧
12      <LIST OF><UNOCCUPIED ELEMENT1><END LIST> ∧
13      X(<R1> ∈ rmgr.ar))
14
15  spec G ((ixl.ma[0] = ixlTbl[<R2>].from ∧
16           Xixl.ma[0] = ixlTbl[<R2>].to) ⇒
17           (ixl.req[0] = <R2> ∧
18           <LIST OF><UNOCCUPIED ELEMENT2><END LIST> ∧
19           X(<R2> ∈ rmgr.ar)))
20
21  spec G ((ixl.ma[1] = ixlTbl[<R3>].from ∧
22           Xixl.ma[1] = ixlTbl[<R3>].to) ⇒
23           (ixl.req[1] = <R3> ∧
24           ixl.ptCmd[<POINT3>] = <POINTSTATE3> ∧
25           ixl.ptSts[<POINT3>] = ixl.ptCmd[<POINT3>] ∧
26           <LIST OF><UNOCCUPIED ELEMENT3><END LIST> ∧
27           X(<R3> ∈ rmgr.ar)))
28
29  spec G ((ixl.ma[1] = ixlTbl[<R2>].from ∧
30           Xixl.ma[1] = ixlTbl[<R2>].to) ⇒
31           (ixl.req[1] = <R2> ∧
32           <LIST OF><UNOCCUPIED ELEMENT2><END LIST> ∧
33           X(<R2> ∈ rmgr.ar)))
34
35  spec G (( $\bigwedge_{r=1}^{10} \bigwedge_{e \in \text{ixlTbl}[r].\text{elems}} \neg \text{ixl.occ}[e] \Rightarrow \mathbf{X} \text{ EoT}$ )
36
37  initact frame := ∅;
38 end scenario

```

5 System Test Specification Templates

As stated in Section 1.2, SCSL system test specifications consist of two parts: the collaboration and the schedule. Both parts have a re-usable structure for the system IXL tests discussed here; this suggests to specify templates that can be instantiated for each concrete system test.

Each system can be instantiated from the template shown in Listing 17.

Listing 17: System test specification template.

```

1 systemtest <SYSTEST NAME>
2   c : collaboration
3     <COLLABORATION SPEC>

```

```

4  end collaboration
5
6  schedule
7    <SCHEDULE SPEC>
8  end schedule
9  end systemtest

```

The template token <SYSTEMTEST NAME> stands for a unique system test name, to be supplied when instantiating a concrete system test specification from this template.

The templates for collaboration specifications and schedules are introduced below.

5.1 Collaboration Template

The objects to be registered in a collaboration are (1) (linear) track segments, (2) points, (3) the IXL, and (4) trains. Moreover, an auxiliary object (5) route manager serving as a data store is needed. Segments and points are the same for all system tests, since the railway network under consideration is static.¹³ They may, however, have different initial states (occupied/ not occupied, actual point position `plus` or `minus`). Some trains may already exist initially and have an initial position on one of the segments, but for the normal behaviour tests considered here, they never reside initially on a point, and they never have an initial movement authority (MA) beyond the segment they are residing on. Other trains are dynamically created during system tests, entering the network from segments `b10` or `b14`. All trains need to request an MA as a first step before proceeding through the network.

Track segments and points share static interfaces with the IXL: Both element types send `occupied/vacant` information to the IXL; additionally, points send position information (`plus / minus`) to the IXL and accept `set-position-commands` from the IXL. Each train has a `train-to-IXL` interface where requests for MA are communicated and an `IXL-to-train` interface where MAs are transmitted. If a train already exists in the network at start-of-test time, these interfaces are declared in the collaboration. Otherwise, they are dynamically created when a train occurs. In any case, these interfaces are removed when a train exits the network.

These considerations suggest the collaboration template in Listing 18 that is usable for all system tests required.

Listing 18: Collaboration template for system tests.

```

1  <COLLABORATION SPEC> ::=
2    sb10 : <INSTANCE OF> Segment(occ = <B>);
3    st10 : <INSTANCE OF> Segment(occ = <B>);
4    pt11 : <INSTANCE OF> Point(occ = false, ptCmd = <PP>, ptSts = <PP>);
5    st12 : <INSTANCE OF> Segment(occ = <B>);

```

¹³ We do not consider here the case where construction measures change the network.

```

6  pt13 : <INSTANCE OF> Point(occ = false, ptCmd = <PP>, ptSts = <PP>);
7  st14 : <INSTANCE OF> Segment(occ = <B>);
8  st20 : <INSTANCE OF> Segment(occ = <B>);
9  sb14 : <INSTANCE OF> Segment(occ = <B>);
10 ixl : Ixl(req = {0,...}, occ = {undef,...}, ptSts = {undef,...},
11      ptCmd = {undef,...}, ma = {undef,...});
12 rmgr : RouteMgr(ar = ∅, createTrainCnd = <CTCND>, maReqCnd = <MARCND>);
13 tr : Train[TMAX] = {<TRAIN>, ...};
14 -- static interfaces
15 interface from sb10.occ to ixl.occ[b10];
16 interface from st10.occ to ixl.occ[t10];
17 interface from pt11.occ to ixl.occ[t11];
18 interface from st12.occ to ixl.occ[t12];
19 interface from pt13.occ to ixl.occ[t13];
20 interface from st14.occ to ixl.occ[t14];
21 interface from st20.occ to ixl.occ[t20];
22 interface from sb14.occ to ixl.occ[b14];
23 interface from pt11.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t11];
24 interface from pt13.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t13];
25 interface from ixl.ptCmd[t11] to pt11.ptCmd;
26 interface from ixl.ptCmd[t13] to pt13.ptCmd;
27 -- train-IXL interfaces for trains initially residing in the network
28 <LIST OF> interface from tr[<IDX>].req to ixl.req[<IDX>];
29 <LIST OF> interface from ixl.ma[<IDX>] to tr[<IDX>].ma;

```

Observe that the IXL instance *ixl* is always created with parameter values indicating “undefined”. The IXL needs a first operation cycle to collect inputs from track elements and trains, whereafter its input parameters become well-defined. Similarly, the IXL sends command value `undef` to points which means that points should not change their actual position until a defined command value arrives.

For the instantiation of a concrete collaboration from the template shown in Listing 18, the following rules apply.

1. Template token <INSTANCE OF> means that exactly one instance of the following text should be created.
2. Template token <LIST OF> means that a (possibly empty) list of the following text should be created.
3. Template token has to be replaced by a Boolean value `true` or `false` during template instantiation.
4. Template token <PP> has to be replaced by a point position value `plus` or `minus` during template instantiation.
5. Template token <CTCND> is replaced by a Boolean array constant of length TMAX written in syntax `{true,...}` or `{false,...}`. The choice of either `true` or `false` values depends on the system test and is specified in the system test directive.
6. Template token <MARCND> is replaced by a Boolean array constant of length TMAX written in syntax `{true,...}` or `{false,...}`. The choice of either

`true` or `false` values depends on the system test and is specified in the system test directive.

7. Template token `<IDX>` has to be replaced by an index value for trains (range from 0 to 5) during template instantiation.
8. Template token `<POS>` has to be replaced by a track segment identifier (one of the values `{b10, t10, t12, t14, t20, b14}`) during template instantiation.
9. Template token `<TRAIN>` has to be replaced by `null` (= “no train”) or by a train instance specification `Train(pos = <POS>, ma = <POS>, req = 0)` during template instantiation.
10. All other syntactic elements in the template should occur without changes in any concrete instance.
11. When selecting concrete values for tokens ``, `<PP>`, `<IDX>`, `<POS>`, the following rules apply:
 - (a) If all entries in `tr : Train[6]` are null, then all occupied flags for segments must be set to false.
 - (b) If some `tr[i]` is not null, then the pos-value of `tr[i] = Train(pos,ma,req=0)` must be a segment name whose occupied flag `occ` is set to true.
 - (c) Conversely, if some segment `s` is marked as occupied, there must exist a train instance `tr[i]` whose position value is `s`.
 - (d) For all train instances `tr[i] = Train(pos,ma,req=0)`, the `ma`-value must be identical to the `pos`-value. This means that initially, the train does not have a movement authority beyond the segment it is currently residing on.
12. The `<LIST OF>` interface specifications must correspond to the trains that are not null in the `tr : Train[6]` specification. The index values `<IDX>` in the interface specification list must correspond to the indexes of the train instances (not null) in `tr`.
13. Non-null entries in array `tr : Train[6]` should always occur at the beginning of the array. The corresponding interface entries in the two `<LIST OF>`-lists should occur in the same ascending order.
14. The declaration `tr : Train[6] = <TRAIN>, ...;` requires exactly 6 train entries in the array. The ellipses `"..."` are interpreted as C syntax, where `T[6] a = 0, ...;` is interpreted, for example, as an array of 6 zeroes.

5.2 Template for Test Schedules

The schedule part of a system test specification can be instantiated from the template shown in Listing 19.

Listing 19: Template for system test schedules.

```

1 <SCHEDULE SPEC> ::=
2   <INCOMING TRAIN SCHED>
3   || <TRAVERSAL SCHED>
4   || <ROUTE RESOLUTION SCHED>
5   || <STOP WITHOUT MA SCHED>
```

```

6  || <SYSTEST NAME>(ixl,rmgr)
7  || CoverageObserver( ixl, rmgr );

```

The template tokens occurring in Listing 19 and their usage are explained in the following set of rules.

1. Template token <INCOMING TRAIN SCHED> has one entry for each train that should be incoming on **b10** or **b14** during test execution and therefore do *not* already reside on one of the segments at test start. Each entry is an elementary scenario instance

$$\text{IncomingTrain}(\langle \text{IDX} \rangle, c, \langle \text{INPOS} \rangle, \text{rmgr}).$$

Template token <IDX> is instantiated to an index i in range 0 to 5 and references an array element $tr[i]$ with value `null`: *IncomingTrain()* scenario instances never refer to an already existing train. Token <INPOS> has values **b10** or **b14**, provided that no train is already residing on these segments at start-of-test. If all trains used in a system test already reside in the network at test start, the <INCOMING TRAIN SCHED> is empty. If several trains are specified, they are separated by the parallel operator `||`.

2. Template token <TRAVERSAL SCHED> is a parallel composition (`||`-operator) of <TRAVERSAL SPEC> entries. For each train, one <TRAVERSAL SPEC> entry is generated for each route the train is supposed to traverse or use for leaving the network.

One <TRAVERSAL SPEC> entry is of the form

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(\text{RequestMA}(\langle \text{IDX} \rangle, c, \langle \text{ROUTE ID} \rangle, \text{rmgr}); \\
 &\quad \text{Traverse}(tr[\langle \text{IDX} \rangle], \langle \text{ROUTE SPEC} \rangle)),
 \end{aligned}$$

if the train remains in the network after traversal. If the entry specifies how a train leaves the network the <TRAVERSAL SPEC> entry is of the form

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(\text{RequestMA}(\langle \text{IDX} \rangle, c, \langle \text{ROUTE ID} \rangle, \text{rmgr}); \\
 &\quad \text{OutgoingTrain}(tr[\langle \text{IDX} \rangle], c, \langle \text{SEG} \rangle, \langle \text{EXIT SEG} \rangle)).
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, the route referenced in <ROUTE ID> must be one of the routes for exiting the network; these are routes number 9 and 10. On these routes, the train starts on a last segment <SEG> *inside* the network and immediately exits via one of the exit/entry segments (parameter <EXIT SEG>). The exit segments are **b10** (in the case of route 10) or **b14** (in the case of route 9).

For both variants of traversal specifications, <IDX> is the index of the train to whom the <TRAVERSAL SPEC> applies. It is fixed for the whole <TRAVERSAL SPEC>. `ROUTE ID` is the number of a route the train requests a movement authority for. The number must be registered in the interlocking table, and a request for MA can only be performed for routes that directly connect with their first element to the actual train position or to the last element of the route the train is actually travelling on. In the *Traverse()*-scenario instance,

<ROUTE SPEC> consists of the sequence of track elements associated with the route. <SEG> $\in \{t10, t12, t14, t20\}$ is a segment inside the network and must coincide with the last element of the route specified in the previous MA request. <EXIT SEG> $\in \{b10, b14\}$ is the exit segment directly connected to <SEG> that is traversed by the train to exit the network.

The MA request and its associated route traversal are sequentially composed since the route traversal may only start *after* the route has been allocated to the train. The allocate-traverse pairs and allocate-outgoing pairs of the traversal specification, however, are composed by the parallel operator. This is because the allocation of the next route can already be performed *before* the train has reached the last element of its currently allocated route.

3. Template token <ROUTE RESOLUTION SCHED> contains the schedule for all route resolutions. It is a parallel composition of entries

$$Resolve(tr[<IDX>], <ROUTE ID>, rmgr),$$

one for each route that is requested in the test. Parameters ($tr[<IDX>]$, <ROUTE ID>) have to match with a corresponding request for MA.

4. Template token <STOP WITHOUT MA SCHED> is a parallel composition of entries

$$StopWithoutMA(tr[<IDX>]),$$

one for each train occurring in the test.

5. Template token <SYSTEST NAME> stands for the name of the system test; its associated elementary scenario instance

$$<SYSTEST NAME>(ixl, rmgr)$$

contains the test-specific oracle checking safe IXL behaviour during the system test execution.

6. The *CoverageObserver()* is always added as the last scenario instance of the parallel composition. There are no template parameters to instantiate.

6 Generation of System Tests

6.1 Generated Route Allocation Tests (Test Class 1)

The GPT received the following directive for generating (1) an elementary scenario instance of Listing 13, (2) a collaboration specification, and (3) a system test schedule for all relevant route allocation tests.

Generate all route allocation tests, one system test for each possible sequence of routes starting at entry/exit elements **b10** or **b14** and ending at the opposite entry/exit element. For each sequence of routes it must be ensured that the first route directly connects to the entry element and the end of the last route connects directly to the exit element. The route in between connects to the first route with its start element (component

$ixlTbl[r].from$ in the IXL table entry for route r) and ends at the first element of the last route (component $ixlTbl[r].to$).

For each system test, create a $\langle SYSTEST\ NAME \rangle$ according to the naming schema

$$\langle SYSTEST\ NAME \rangle ::= SysTestC1_ \langle NUM \rangle,$$

where $\langle NUM \rangle$ is a unique number within test class 1. Create an elementary scenario with name $\langle SYSTEST\ NAME \rangle$ from the template in Listing 13, following the rules underneath Listing 13. Create a system test specification according to the template in Listing 17.

For its collaboration specification part, use the template in Listing 18 and initialise the route manager $rmgr$ with $createTrainCnd = \{\mathbf{true}, \dots\}$ and $maReqCnd = \{\mathbf{true}, \dots\}$. For the train array tr , all 6 elements are initially \mathbf{null} (as specified in the test schedule, the only train used in these tests is dynamically created and will be inserted into $tr[0]$). Initialise all points with a position that needs to be changed for the allocated routes by commands from the IXL. The route-specific point positions are specified in the $ixlTbl$ specified in Table 1, component pp . All segments are initialised with $occ = \mathbf{false}$, since the network is initially empty for all system tests of this class. The list of train-IXL interfaces is empty, since initially, no trains exist; the only train and its interfaces are generated dynamically, as specified in the test schedule. Furthermore, observe all template instantiation rules specified underneath Listing 18.

The schedule part of the system test specification should be instantiated according to the template in Listing 19, observing the rules specified underneath the listing. We only need one instance of $IncomingTrain()$ per test, where the train is indexed by zero and positioned either on $b10$ or $b14$. One $\langle TRAVERSAL\ SCHED \rangle$ must be allocated for the train with index zero, consisting of three $\langle TRAVERSAL\ SPEC \rangle$ s composed in parallel as explained in Section 5.2. The first and the second $\langle TRAVERSAL\ SPEC \rangle$ use a $Traverse()$ instance after the $RequestMA()$ instance. The third entry uses an $OutgoingTrain()$ instance after the $RequestMA()$ instance.

6.2 Generated Conflict Tests (Test Class 2)

Succeeding Train Tests (Class 2.1) For this test class introduced in Section 4.2, train 0 traverses the route sequence first, while train 1 follows on the same sequence with a delay enforced by MA request conditions. The following directives are passed to the GPT for generating (1) an elementary scenario instance of Listing 14, (2) a collaboration specification, and (3) a system test schedule for all relevant succeeding train tests.

Recall that the selection of routes for this test class has already been explained in the context of Listing 14.

1. For this class of system tests, the naming convention is

$$\langle SYSTEST\ NAME \rangle ::= SysTestC21_ \langle NUM \rangle,$$

where $\langle \text{NUM} \rangle$ is the test number within Class 2.1.

2. In all tests of Class 2.1, two trains are involved. They are registered with index 0 and index 1 in the tr -array of the collaboration, respectively.
3. Train 0 always acts as the leading train, train 1 as the follow-up train.
4. Train 0 is already instantiated in the tr -array of collaboration c at index zero. Therefore, $c.tr$ is declared in c as

$$tr : \text{Train}[\text{TMAX}] = \{ \text{Train}(\text{pos} = \langle \text{ENTRY SEG} \rangle, \text{ma} = \langle \text{ENTRY SEG} \rangle, \text{req} = 0), \\ \text{null}, \text{null}, \text{null}, \text{null}, \text{null} \};$$

where template parameter $\langle \text{ENTRY SEG} \rangle$ denotes the identifier of the entry segment of route $\langle \text{R1} \rangle$, that is, **b10** for tests with routes in direction UP, and **b14** for tests with routes in direction DOWN. The associated interface declarations in the collaboration are

$$\text{interface from } tr[0].\text{req} \text{ to } ixl.\text{req}[0]; \\ \text{interface from } ixl.\text{ma}[0] \text{ to } tr[0].\text{ma};$$

5. The route manager $rmgr$ in the collaboration c is declared with

$$\langle \text{CTND} \rangle ::= \{ \text{false}, \text{true}, \text{false}, \text{false}, \text{false}, \text{false} \}$$

because train 1 is already created in the declaration of $c.tr$, and the correct timing for the creation of train 1 is already ensured by the precondition of the $\text{IncomingTrain}()$ instance. Furthermore, the template parameter $\langle \text{MARCND} \rangle$ of the $rmgr$ declaration is instantiated as

$$\langle \text{MARCND} \rangle ::= \{ \text{true}, \text{true}, \text{false}, \text{false}, \text{false}, \text{false} \},$$

since both trains may apply for MAs whenever the precondition of the respective $\text{RequestMA}()$ -instance is fulfilled.

Note that we do not rely on train 1 issuing MA requests after train 0. On the contrary, any request order is permitted, provided that the preconditions of the respective $\text{RequestMA}()$ instances are satisfied. The objective of Class 2.1 tests is to verify that the IXL enforces the correct order of route allocations based solely on track occupancy and already allocated routes, independent of the request order generated by the trains.

6. For the second train 1, an instance of

$$\text{IncomingTrain}(\text{idx} = 1, c, \langle \text{ENTRY SEG} \rangle, rmgr)$$

is produced and inserted into the schedule for template parameter $\langle \text{INCOMING TRAIN SCHED} \rangle$, as explained in Section 5.2. Recall that train 1 is initially positioned in the same entry segment [instance of $\langle \text{ENTRY SEG} \rangle$] as train 0. The precondition of $\text{IncomingTrain}()$ ensures that train 1 is only created *after* train 0 has vacated the entry segment.

7. The `<TRAVERSAL SCHED>` parameter of the test schedule is instantiated for both trains with a parallel composition of three `<TRAVERSAL SPEC>` instances. The first two traversal specifications consist of $(RequestMA(); Traverse())$ pairs, the third is a $(RequestMA(); OutgoingTrain())$ pair. For the first train, `<IDX>` is instantiated with index 0, for the second train with index 1. For each train, the first `<TRAVERSAL SPEC>` uses `<R1>` as `<ROUTE ID>` and the elements of `<R1>` as `<ROUTE SPEC>`. The second `<TRAVERSAL SPEC>` uses `<R2>` as `<ROUTE ID>` and the elements of `<R2>` as `<ROUTE SPEC>`. The third `<TRAVERSAL SPEC>` uses `<R3>` as `<ROUTE ID>`, the first element of `<R3>` as the instance of `<SEG>` in the instantiation of $OutgoingTrain()$ and the last element of `<R3>` for template parameter `<EXIT SEG>`.
8. Generate one test for every succession of three routes in UP direction, and one for every succession in DOWN direction.

Conflicting Route Tests (Class 2.2) For this test class, the following directives were given to the GPT for generating (1) elementary scenario instances of Listing 15 and Listing 16, (2) a collaboration specification, and (3) a system test schedule for all relevant conflict tests.

1. For this class of system tests, the naming convention is

$$\langle \text{SYSTEST NAME} \rangle ::= SysTestC22_ \langle \text{NUM} \rangle,$$

where `<NUM>` is the test number within Class 2.2.

2. According to Table 2, four system tests have to be generated.
3. For the first two rows, instances of the template in Listing 15 are used as elementary scenario instances for the system test, for rows 3 and 4, instances of the template in Listing 16.
4. For the tests identified in the first two rows of Table 2, all three trains with indexes 0,1,2 are declared in the tr -array of the collaboration as

```
tr : Train[TMAX] =
  { Train(pos = b10, ma = b10, req = 0),
    Train(pos = <SEG1>, ma = <SEG1>, req = 0),
    Train(pos = <SEG2>, ma = <SEG2>, req = 0),
    null, null, null};
```

where `<SEG1>` is the elem-entry for train Tr1 in Table 2 and `<SEG2>` is the elem-entry for train Tr2 in Table 2. The interfaces are declared as already explained for Class 2.1 as

```
interface from tr[0].req to ixl.req[0];
interface from ixl.ma[0] to tr[0].ma;
```

for train 0 and analogously for trains 1 and 2.

5. Analogously, for the tests identified in rows 3 and 4 of Table 2, two trains with indexes 0,1 are declared in the *tr*-array of the collaboration as

```
tr : Train[TMAX] =
    {Train(pos = t12, ma = t12, req = 0),
     Train(pos = t20, ma = t20, req = 0),
     null, null, null, null};
```

The interfaces are declared as described for three-train case.

6. Consequently, no *IncomingTrain()*-instances are needed in the schedule for Class 2.2 tests.
7. The route manager *rmgr* in both collaborations (three-train tests and two-train tests) is declared with

```
<CTND> ::= {false, false, false, false, false, false}
```

because all trains are already created in the declaration of *c.tr*. Furthermore, the template parameter <MARCND> of the *rmgr* declaration is instantiated for the three-train tests as

```
<MARCND> ::= {true, false, true, false, false, false},
```

since both trains 0 and 2 may apply for MAs immediately (the second MA application of train 0 is controlled inside the elementary scenario instance created from Listing 15). For train 1, application for MA is initially disabled, but will also be enabled during the test execution in the scenario instance of Listing 15.

For the two-train tests, all MA applications are always enabled, so

```
<MARCND> ::= {true, true, false, false, false, false}.
```

8. The <TRAVERSAL SCHED> template of the system test schedule is instantiated for the three-train tests by creating two <TRAVERSAL SPEC> entries of the form

```
(RequestMA(0, c, <ROUTE ID>, rmgr);
  Traverse(tr[0], <ROUTE SPEC>)),
```

for train 0. In the first entry, the <ROUTE ID> is the first route number of Tr0.rMA in Table 2, and <ROUTE SPEC> is the sequence of elements of this route, as taken from the IXL table. For the second <TRAVERSAL SPEC>, the <ROUTE ID> is the second route number of Tr0.rMA in Table 2, and <ROUTE SPEC> is the sequence of elements of this route.

For train 1 and train 2, the <TRAVERSAL SCHED> only has one <TRAVERSAL SPEC> entry of the same form. The <ROUTE ID> is the route number of Tr1.rMA and Tr2.rMA in Table 2, respectively, and <ROUTE SPEC> is the sequence of elements of this route.

Recall that only the elementary scenario instances inside one traversal specification are sequentially composed:

```
RequestMA(); Traverse() or RequestMA(); OutgoingTrain().
```

All traversal specifications, including several traversal specifications belonging to the same train, are composed in parallel. Their effective execution order is controlled by the preconditions of the involved RequestMA() instances and, for Class 2.2 three-train tests, by the additional route-manager conditions specified in the corresponding elementary scenario instance.

9. The <TRAVERSAL SCHED> template is instantiated for the two-train tests as follows. For each train, two <TRAVERSAL SPEC> entries are created. The first entry consists of a *RequestMA();Traverse()* sequence, the second of a *RequestMA();OutgoingTrain()* sequence. As usual, all traversal specs are composed in parallel, since the activation conditions for each spec are encoded in the precondition of the *RequestMA()* scenario instance.

For train 0, the first <TRAVERSAL SPEC> entry uses route <R1>, and the second uses route <R2>. For train 1, the first <TRAVERSAL SPEC> entry uses route <R3>, and the second uses route <R2>. The corresponding route specifications are taken from the IXL table.

7 Validation of Generated Tests

To identify the appropriate validation measures to be performed on the SCSL specifications, the generated artefacts, and the tool platform it is useful to start with a risk analysis. This approach is in line with the validation measures for verification processes and artefacts suggested in standards for safety-critical systems [3,18]. The two main risks that could materialise if system tests are erroneous or the execution environment is faulty are

- R1.** Erroneous SUT behaviour remains undetected.
- R2.** The true coverage of test objectives achieved during the test suite execution is less than the recorded coverage.

In the context of the topics discussed here, the main objective of validation is to mitigate these risks to a degree where certification credit can be obtained for the test results.

Both risks can occur due to errors inside the test execution platform. To avoid this, tools have to be *qualified* or *validated*. This topic is outside the scope of this paper, but has been extensively handled in the literature [3,18,1,8].

In this section we focus on how **R1** and **R2** can be caused by (1) erroneous SCSL specifications or (2) erroneous generation of tests by a GPT and how these potential causes can be avoided.

7.1 Mitigation of Risk R1

A static analysis of reusable and test-specific scenarios shows that the final decision about when to end a test execution and how to set the verdict is taken in

the scenario instances generated from test-specific templates (Section 4). Some reusable scenarios may contribute to the decision that a test execution fails, but they cannot force the final verdict to be **pass**, since they do not set the end-of-test criterion. Therefore, risk **R1** can only materialise if one of the following errors occurs in the test-specific scenario instances, or if the test schedule fails to execute the intended scenario instances.

Therefore, risk **R1** can only materialise if one of the following errors occurs in the test-specific scenario instances, or if the test schedule fails to execute the intended scenario instances.

- R1.1** The test-specific scenario instance (created from one of the templates in Section 4) fails to detect erroneous SUT behaviour although the relevant erroneous behaviour occurs during the test execution.
- R1.2** The test-specific scenario instance terminates early, before all intended test objectives have been stimulated and checked.
- R1.3** The test schedule fails to execute the intended scenario instances.

Regarding risk **R1.3**, a manual review is required, because the intended ordering and concurrency structure of a test is part of the verification intent and cannot be derived from the generated schedule alone. The review can be facilitated by automatically creating a verbal description of the schedule from the schedule’s abstract syntax tree representation and using this description as input for the review process.

Risk **R1.2** is addressed in two steps. First, the generated test-specific scenario instance is checked by static analysis to ensure that the end-of-test formula from the associated template has been instantiated correctly. Second, the end-of-test formulas in the templates are manually verified once.

For the route allocation tests, for example (Listing 13), it is checked whether the last LTL formula has been copied into the template instantiation with correct replacement of template parameters `<SEG>`, `<EXITSEG>`, and `<ROUTEID>`. These need to be the values of the test’s exit route. Such a static analysis can be easily mechanised.

In this template, `EoT` is set to `true` when the segments of the exit route (the last route to be covered in a Class 1 test) are unoccupied again after the exit route had been allocated before, but is now resolved. This is exactly the intended termination criterion, provided that the `rmgr.ar`-variable is set correctly (this is verified in the context of **R1.1.2** below).

Risk **R1.1** can materialise if the following subordinate risks occur.

- R1.1.1** The test-specific scenario template contains logical formula errors (this includes missing checks to be specified in formulas).
- R1.1.2** Variable `rmgr.ar` contains wrong route identifiers.
- R1.1.3** The interfaces (the “wiring”) between track elements and IXL and trains and IXL, as specified in the collaboration, is faulty.
- R1.1.4** The template instantiation uses erroneous values for template parameters.
- R1.1.5** The stimulations of the SUT are faulty or incomplete.

Risk **R1.1.5** is mitigated by checking all elementary scenario types performing writes to the SUT or changing the system configuration by dynamic allocations of trains. These are *IncomingTrain()*, *OutgoingTrain()*, *RequestMA()*. A light-weight formal verification (not shown here) of these scenario types proves that the writes to the SUT are complete and correct, provided that all template parameters involved are instantiated correctly in the test schedule (risk **R1.1.4**).

Regarding risk **R1.1.4**, a static analysis of the generated elementary scenario can be performed. This can be easily mechanised:

1. Route parameters (<R1>, <ROUTEID>, ...) need to be instantiated in the correct order with the routes intended for the test execution.
2. Point parameters (<POINT1>, ...) need to be instantiated with the point identification found in the IXL table for the associated route.
3. Point state parameters (<POINTSTATE1>, ...) need to be instantiated with the point states required for the respective route according to the IXL table.
4. The <LIST OF><UNOCCUPIED ELEMENT><END LIST> parameters need to be instantiated with the tail of the track element list found for the given route in the IXL table.

Note that these checks are also applied to all scenario instantiations in the test schedule where template parameters are used, as, for example, in

$$\textit{IncomingTrain}(\langle \text{IDX} \rangle, c, \langle \text{INPOS} \rangle, \textit{rmgr}).$$

For avoiding risk **R1.1.3**, it is easy to check in a mechanised way that the static information in a generated collaboration is specified correctly. This includes the declarations of track elements, the IXL, the route manager, initial trains, and the associated interfaces. Moreover, the dynamic creation of trains and their interfaces is encapsulated in reusable scenario type *IncomingTrain()*. A simple static analysis shows that both the train creation and the two interface creations are correct in the scenario's initial action.

This validation argument assumes that the concrete interfaces used in simulations or real-world tests are correctly abstracted by the interface specifications in the collaboration. Validation of this abstraction layer is outside the scope of this paper.

To verify that risk **R1.1.2** will not occur, we perform light-weight formal verification with the following steps.

1. Static analysis shows that variable *rmgr.ar* is only changed by elementary scenarios *RequestMA()* and *Resolve()* (Section 3.3): these are the only scenarios where *rmgr.ar* is contained in their frame-variable.
2. The LTL specification in *RequestMA()* ensures that route *r* is inserted into *rmgr.ar* ($r \in \textit{rmgr.ar}$) simultaneously with the event that an MA for *r* is awarded to the train ($c.tr[idx].ma = \textit{ixlTbl}[r].to$).
3. The LTL specification in *Resolve()* shows that route *r* is removed from *rmgr.ar* in the next step after the train is contained completely in the last segment of this route.

Since the relevant behaviours of both *RequestMA()* and *Resolve()* have been checked and no other scenario performs changes on this variable, we conclude that risk **R1.1.2** is mitigated.

Regarding risk **R1.1.1**, a light-weight formal verification of the LTL formulas specified in the test-specific scenario templates is performed along the following lines.

1. It is checked that the route-related safety conditions are stated correctly. For Listing 13, this is the LTL formula in line 3 stating that at most one route may be allocated during this test. For succeeding train tests, only the safety conditions for MAs need to be checked, since connected routes in the same direction are never in conflict with each other. For the conflicting route test templates, the safety condition states correctly that conflicting routes may never be simultaneously allocated.
2. It is checked that the safety conditions regarding MA are stated correctly. These checks cover the three families of test-specific oracle clauses: route-allocation safety, correct point setting, and admissibility of MA assignment with respect to requests and route occupancy. In the template in Listing 13, for example, the LTL specification in line 5 states that route allocation for a route with specified entry segment and end segment is performed only when (a) the route has really been requested by a train, (b) the point on the route is in the correct state specified in the IXL table, all route elements in front of the requesting train are unoccupied.
The other LTL formulas about route allocation have a similar structure and can be verified just as easily.

Note that none of the validation steps discussed in the context of risk **R1** make any correctness assumptions about the GPT-based generation process. All validation steps are performed either on reusable scenario types or on the concrete generated scenario types, collaborations, and test schedules.

7.2 Mitigation of Risk R2

To mitigate risk **R2** (erroneous test coverage information), a *test coverage monitor* has been introduced by elementary scenario type *CoverageObserver()* in Section 3.3. In every test execution, an instance of *CoverageObserver()* monitors and records the coverage of test objectives *actually achieved during test execution* and does not rely on any correctness properties of the generated test specifications.

It is trivial to check in the generated test schedules that such an instance is part of every test specification. Recall that we do not consider tool errors in this paper. Therefore, the causes for erroneous coverage recordings to be investigated here are

- R2.1** a logical error in scenario type *CoverageObserver()*,
- R2.2** a test execution fails to complete, but still coverage is recorded for this execution,

R2.3 erroneous writes to the global coverage recording graph C (Section 3.1) by other scenario instances, or

R2.4 a wiring error in the collaboration specification, as already discussed in the context of risk **R1**.

Regarding wiring errors in the collaboration (**R2.4**), the validation measures have already been discussed above. The absence of writes to C by other scenario instances (**R2.3**) can be checked by simple static analysis of the elementary scenario types involved, including the scenario types generated by a GPT from templates: It is easy to see that no other scenario types or templates refer to C .

The cause for **R2.2** is more subtle: the instance of *CoverageObserver()* monitors *trigger conditions* indicating that a test objective will be fulfilled *if the test terminates without failure*. From the specification of scenario type *CoverageObserver()*, we see that a write-back to C only occurs if the **pass**-verdict is observed. From the validation measures in the context of **R1** we know that the test-specific scenario instances will only set the **EoT** (end of test flag) if all route traversals involved in the objectives to be tested have been completed. Only then the test verdict will become visible, and we know from the analysis of **R1** that the verdict will only be **pass** if all test objectives have been tested without errors. Consequently, the instance of *CoverageObserver()* will only write coverage information back to C if the test has been successfully completed.

To investigate **R2.1**, we perform a light-weight formal verification. As a first step, we observe that the initial action correctly copies the coverage graph C to corresponding auxiliary variables and that the sets $E_{2,3}, E_4$ contain exactly the correct edges associated with test classes 2,3,4.

As a second step, we observe from the LTL specifications in lines 2 and 3 that the auxiliary variables are copied back to C if and only if the test terminates with verdict **pass**. It remains to show that if the test is passed the correct coverage information is contained in the auxiliary functions c'_N, c'_E .

In step 3, we check that all assignments to the coverage recording functions c'_N, c'_E are correct, provided that the trigger conditions are correct. This is checked by a simple case analysis.

1. The first condition-action loop sets $c'_N(r)$ to **true** for exactly one argument r which is also referenced in the trigger condition.
2. The second condition-action loop sets $c'_E(r_1, r_2)$ to **true** for exactly the pair of routes referenced in the trigger condition.
3. The same holds for the third condition-action loop.

As step 4, we check that the three trigger conditions are correct. In all three conditions, the first conjunct just states that the action is only triggered if necessary, that is, if the coverage functions have not already recorded coverage for the route or for the pair of routes under consideration. We can now focus on the remaining conjuncts of each trigger condition.

1. In the first condition-action loop, $r \in rmgr.ar$ indicates that some train has allocated route r . If the test execution passes, we know from the discussion

about risk **R1** that the train will actually have traversed the route r . This is exactly the coverage criterion we are looking for in Class 1, provided that $r \in rmgr.ar$ is set by another scenario instance if and only if a train has allocated route r .

2. In the second condition-action loop, conjunct $r_1 \in rmgr.ar$ is a necessary condition for the trigger. This means that some train has already allocated route r_1 . The last conjunct ($\bigvee_{i \in \text{TrainId}} ixl.req[i] = r_2$) states that there must exist another train simultaneously requesting MA for r_2 . (We have explained in Section 3.3 why this train is distinct from the one possessing MA for r_1 .) This is exactly the condition for checking route conflicts (Class 2) or safe sequencing of routes (Class 3).
3. In the third condition-action loop, conjunct ($\bigvee_{\substack{i,j \in \text{TrainId} \\ i \neq j}} (ixl.req[i] = r_1 \wedge ixl.req[j] = r_2)$) states the correct trigger condition for Class 4: two trains need to simultaneously request routes that are associated with Class 4 as a pair.

The argument above is based on the assumption that the $rmgr.ar$ variable is always updated correctly. This, however, has already been verified in the context of risk **R1**.

In conclusion, sub-risks **R2.1** — **R2.1** could all be discharged, so the coverage recording is trustworthy, provided that the underlying execution platform has been validated or qualified as required for the intended assurance level. Again, no assumptions about the behavioural correctness of GPT-based transformations have been made: Either reusable scenario types or the concrete scenario types generated by the GPT are verified by light-weight formal verification in the former case or static analysis in the latter case are performed.

8 Evaluation

For the approach described in this paper, OpenAI ChatGPT, GPT-5.5 Thinking model¹⁴ was used.

The GPT-based system test generation was preceded by a review phase, where the GPT was requested to comment on the correctness and clarity of

1. reusable elementary scenario types and the associated textual explanations (Section 3.3),
2. instantiation rules for test-specific scenario templates (Section 4),
3. instantiation rules for the collaboration and scheduling templates (Section 5), and
4. generation rules for complete system test classes (Section 6).

The effort for this corresponded to that of one person taking part in a manual peer review of a verification plan describing how test procedures should be programmed. (A manual review would involve at least two persons.)

¹⁴ <https://deploymentsafety.openai.com/gpt-5>

After that phase, the GPT was commanded to generate the system tests for all test classes described above. The generation took approximately 5 minutes. These generated system tests (see their documentation in Appendix A generated by the GPT for this paper) were 100% correct with respect to the specified generation rules. We attribute this result mainly to the preceding review phase. Observe that this high degree of generation correctness is not essential from the safety perspective: The validation measures explained above would have uncovered all critical errors during the test execution phase. Instead, the high degree of generation correctness indicates that the approach proposed in the paper can be effectively applied in practice, with less effort for review and less effort for test procedure development (our estimate for manually developing the procedures listed in Appendix A is 3 person days).

9 Conclusion

The application of a GPT for generating system tests from formally defined scenario templates was effective in the sense explained in the evaluation section. In particular, the generated system tests were correct with respect to the specified generation rules, and the effort for producing the test procedures was considerably lower than for a manual development of these procedures.

We attribute this result mainly to two factors. First, the GPT was not used for synthesising complete formal specifications from natural-language requirements. Instead, it was used for systematically instantiating formally defined templates under rule-based guidance. This considerably reduces the degree of freedom in the generation task. Second, the actual generation phase was preceded by a review phase, where the GPT was requested to check the correctness and clarity of the elementary scenario types, the test-specific scenario templates, the collaboration and scheduling templates, and the generation rules for complete test classes. This review phase corresponds to a typical peer review activity for verification plans describing how test procedures should be programmed.

The validation concept described in this paper shows that errors in GPT-generated test specifications are unlikely to result in erroneous test outcomes with safety-critical consequences. Critical errors would be detected during the validation of the generated tests. Their main effect is therefore a reduction of productivity: failures detected during validation have to be analysed, and the GPT-based generation process has to be improved. In our experience, this mainly means improving the generation guidelines, so that the GPT receives more precise and less ambiguous instructions.

The scenario specification language SCSL proved to be effective for designing test scenarios and for validating them. In particular, SCSL encourages a modular specification style, where elementary scenario types can be specified, reviewed, validated, and reused independently. As a consequence, complete system tests can be constructed from smaller and less complex scenario specifications. This is beneficial both for human review and for GPT-based generation.

Together with previous work on system test definitions for autonomous robotics [15], the present results illustrate the wide-spectrum capabilities of SCSL across different classes of cyber-physical systems.

As a next step, we will apply SCSL and GPT-generated tests to the definition of test suites according to the EULYNX standard, which has been designed for harmonising the communication between components of modern railway signalling systems in Europe.¹⁵ This will allow us to investigate the applicability of the proposed approach to standardised interfaces and larger collections of industrially relevant test objectives.

A further goal is to investigate whether the latest large language models are capable of synthesising elementary scenario specifications from natural-language descriptions. Again, it is not required that this synthesis achieves 100% correctness, because the validation measures described in this paper are designed to uncover critical errors. The GPT-based process should, however, be reliable enough to be more effective than writing the formal scenario specifications manually.

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A Generated SCSL Tests

A.1 Class 1 Tests

```

-- =====
-- Generated SCSL tests for Class 1: route allocation tests
-- Generated from main2.tex, using the current Class 1 scenario template,
-- collaboration template, and schedule template.
--
-- Route sequences covered:
--   SysTestC1_1: 1.2.9   (b10 -> b14)
--   SysTestC1_2: 3.4.9   (b10 -> b14)
--   SysTestC1_3: 5.6.10  (b14 -> b10)
--   SysTestC1_4: 7.8.10  (b14 -> b10)
--
-- Checks performed after generation:
-- * every schedule ends with CoverageObserver(ixl, rmgr);
-- * every Class 1 final formula contains X X EoT;
-- * all traversal specifications are composed in parallel;
-- * no template placeholders remain.
-- =====

-- SysTestC1_1: route sequence 1.2.9, entry b10, exit b14
-- =====
elementary scenario SysTestC1_1(ixl : Ixl, rmgr : RouteMgr)

  spec G( |rmgr.ar| <= 1 )

  spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = b10 and X ixl.ma[0] = t12) =>
    (ixl.req[0] = 1 and
     ixl.ptCmd[t11] = plus and
     ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
     not ixl.occ[t10] and
     not ixl.occ[t11] and
     not ixl.occ[t12] and
     X (1 in rmgr.ar)) )

  spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t12 and X ixl.ma[0] = t14) =>
    (ixl.req[0] = 2 and
     ixl.ptCmd[t13] = plus and
     ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
     not ixl.occ[t13] and
     not ixl.occ[t14] and
     X (2 in rmgr.ar)) )

  spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t14 and X ixl.ma[0] = b14) =>
    (ixl.req[0] = 9 and not ixl.occ[b14] and
     X (9 in rmgr.ar and
      F (not ixl.occ[t14] and not ixl.occ[b14] and
        X rmgr.ar = {} and X X EoT))) )

  initact frm := {};
end scenario

systemtest SysTestC1_1
  c : collaboration
  sb10 : Segment(occ = false);
  st10 : Segment(occ = false);
  pt11 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = minus, ptSts = minus);
  st12 : Segment(occ = false);
  pt13 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = minus, ptSts = minus);
  st14 : Segment(occ = false);
  st20 : Segment(occ = false);
  sb14 : Segment(occ = false);
  ixl : Ixl(req = {0, ...}, occ = {undef, ...}, ptSts = {undef, ...},
    ptCmd = {pundef, ...}, ma = {undef, ...});

```

```

rmgr : RouteMgr(ar = {}),
      createTrainCnd = {true, true, true, true, true, true},
      maReqCnd = {true, true, true, true, true, true});
tr : Train[TMAX] = {null, null, null, null, null, null};

-- static interfaces
interface from sb10.occ to ixl.occ[b10];
interface from st10.occ to ixl.occ[t10];
interface from pt11.occ to ixl.occ[t11];
interface from st12.occ to ixl.occ[t12];
interface from pt13.occ to ixl.occ[t13];
interface from st14.occ to ixl.occ[t14];
interface from st20.occ to ixl.occ[t20];
interface from sb14.occ to ixl.occ[b14];
interface from pt11.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t11];
interface from pt13.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t13];
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t11] to pt11.ptCmd;
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t13] to pt13.ptCmd;
end collaboration

schedule
  IncomingTrain(0, c, b10, rmgr)
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 1, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <b10, t10, t11, t12>))
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 2, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <t12, t13, t14>))
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 9, rmgr); OutgoingTrain(tr[0], c, t14, b14))
  || Resolve(tr[0], 1, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[0], 2, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[0], 9, rmgr)
  || StopWithoutMA(tr[0])
  || SysTestC1_1(ixl, rmgr)
  || CoverageObserver(ixl, rmgr)
end schedule
end systemtest

-- =====
-- SysTestC1_2: route sequence 3.4.9, entry b10, exit b14
-- =====
elementary scenario SysTestC1_2(ixl : Ixl, rmgr : RouteMgr)

  spec G( |rmgr.ar| <= 1 )

  spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = b10 and X ixl.ma[0] = t20) =>
    (ixl.req[0] = 3 and
     ixl.ptCmd[t11] = minus and
     ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
     not ixl.occ[t10] and
     not ixl.occ[t11] and
     not ixl.occ[t20] and
     X (3 in rmgr.ar)) )

  spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t20 and X ixl.ma[0] = t14) =>
    (ixl.req[0] = 4 and
     ixl.ptCmd[t13] = minus and
     ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
     not ixl.occ[t13] and
     not ixl.occ[t14] and
     X (4 in rmgr.ar)) )

  spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t14 and X ixl.ma[0] = b14) =>
    (ixl.req[0] = 9 and not ixl.occ[b14] and
     X (9 in rmgr.ar and
      F (not ixl.occ[t14] and not ixl.occ[b14] and
        X rmgr.ar = {} and X X EoT))) )

  initact frm := {};
end scenario

systemtest SysTestC1_2

```

```

c : collaboration
sb10 : Segment(occ = false);
st10 : Segment(occ = false);
pt11 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = plus, ptSts = plus);
st12 : Segment(occ = false);
pt13 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = plus, ptSts = plus);
st14 : Segment(occ = false);
st20 : Segment(occ = false);
sb14 : Segment(occ = false);
ixl : Ixl(req = {0, ...}, occ = {undef, ...}, ptSts = {undef, ...},
          ptCmd = {pundef, ...}, ma = {undef, ...});
rmgr : RouteMgr(ar = {},
                createTrainCnd = {true, true, true, true, true, true},
                maReqCnd = {true, true, true, true, true, true});
tr : Train[TMAX] = {null, null, null, null, null, null};

-- static interfaces
interface from sb10.occ to ixl.occ[b10];
interface from st10.occ to ixl.occ[t10];
interface from pt11.occ to ixl.occ[t11];
interface from st12.occ to ixl.occ[t12];
interface from pt13.occ to ixl.occ[t13];
interface from st14.occ to ixl.occ[t14];
interface from st20.occ to ixl.occ[t20];
interface from sb14.occ to ixl.occ[b14];
interface from pt11.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t11];
interface from pt13.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t13];
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t11] to pt11.ptCmd;
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t13] to pt13.ptCmd;
end collaboration

schedule
  IncomingTrain(0, c, b10, rmgr)
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 3, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <b10, t10, t11, t20>))
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 4, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <t20, t13, t14>))
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 9, rmgr); OutgoingTrain(tr[0], c, t14, b14))
  || Resolve(tr[0], 3, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[0], 4, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[0], 9, rmgr)
  || StopWithoutMA(tr[0])
  || SysTestC1_2(ixl, rmgr)
  || CoverageObserver(ixl, rmgr)
end schedule
end systemtest

-- =====
-- SysTestC1_3: route sequence 5.6.10, entry b14, exit b10
-- =====
elementary scenario SysTestC1_3(ixl : Ixl, rmgr : RouteMgr)

spec G( |rmgr.ar| <= 1 )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = b14 and X ixl.ma[0] = t12) =>
        (ixl.req[0] = 5 and
         ixl.ptCmd[t13] = plus and
         ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
         not ixl.occ[t14] and
         not ixl.occ[t13] and
         not ixl.occ[t12] and
         X (5 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t12 and X ixl.ma[0] = t10) =>
        (ixl.req[0] = 6 and
         ixl.ptCmd[t11] = plus and
         ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
         not ixl.occ[t11] and
         not ixl.occ[t10] and
         X (6 in rmgr.ar)) )

```

```

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t10 and X ixl.ma[0] = b10) =>
        (ixl.req[0] = 10 and not ixl.occ[b10] and
         X (10 in rmgr.ar and
            F (not ixl.occ[t10] and not ixl.occ[b10] and
               X rmgr.ar = {} and X X EoT))) )

initact frm := {};
end scenario

systemtest SysTestC1_3
c : collaboration
  sb10 : Segment(occ = false);
  st10 : Segment(occ = false);
  pt11 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = minus, ptSts = minus);
  st12 : Segment(occ = false);
  pt13 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = minus, ptSts = minus);
  st14 : Segment(occ = false);
  st20 : Segment(occ = false);
  sb14 : Segment(occ = false);
  ixl : Ixl(req = {0, ...}, occ = {undef, ...}, ptSts = {undef, ...},
            ptCmd = {pundef, ...}, ma = {undef, ...});
  rmgr : RouteMgr(ar = {},
                  createTrainCnd = {true, true, true, true, true, true},
                  maReqCnd = {true, true, true, true, true, true});
  tr : Train[TMAX] = {null, null, null, null, null, null};

-- static interfaces
interface from sb10.occ to ixl.occ[b10];
interface from st10.occ to ixl.occ[t10];
interface from pt11.occ to ixl.occ[t11];
interface from st12.occ to ixl.occ[t12];
interface from pt13.occ to ixl.occ[t13];
interface from st14.occ to ixl.occ[t14];
interface from st20.occ to ixl.occ[t20];
interface from sb14.occ to ixl.occ[b14];
interface from pt11.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t11];
interface from pt13.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t13];
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t11] to pt11.ptCmd;
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t13] to pt13.ptCmd;
end collaboration

schedule
  IncomingTrain(0, c, b14, rmgr)
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 5, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <b14, t14, t13, t12>))
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 6, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <t12, t11, t10>))
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 10, rmgr); OutgoingTrain(tr[0], c, t10, b10))
  || Resolve(tr[0], 5, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[0], 6, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[0], 10, rmgr)
  || StopWithoutMA(tr[0])
  || SysTestC1_3(ixl, rmgr)
  || CoverageObserver(ixl, rmgr)
end schedule
end systemtest

-- =====
-- SysTestC1_4: route sequence 7.8.10, entry b14, exit b10
-- =====
elementary scenario SysTestC1_4(ixl : Ixl, rmgr : RouteMgr)

spec G( |rmgr.ar| <= 1 )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = b14 and X ixl.ma[0] = t20) =>
        (ixl.req[0] = 7 and
         ixl.ptCmd[t13] = minus and
         ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
         not ixl.occ[t14] and

```

```

        not ixl.occ[t13] and
        not ixl.occ[t20] and
        X (7 in rmgr.ar) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t20 and X ixl.ma[0] = t10) =>
        (ixl.req[0] = 8 and
         ixl.ptCmd[t11] = minus and
         ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
         not ixl.occ[t11] and
         not ixl.occ[t10] and
         X (8 in rmgr.ar) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t10 and X ixl.ma[0] = b10) =>
        (ixl.req[0] = 10 and not ixl.occ[b10] and
         X (10 in rmgr.ar and
           F (not ixl.occ[t10] and not ixl.occ[b10] and
             X rmgr.ar = {} and X X EoT))) )

initact frm := {};
end scenario

systemtest SysTestC1_4
c : collaboration
  sb10 : Segment(occ = false);
  st10 : Segment(occ = false);
  pt11 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = plus, ptSts = plus);
  st12 : Segment(occ = false);
  pt13 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = plus, ptSts = plus);
  st14 : Segment(occ = false);
  st20 : Segment(occ = false);
  sb14 : Segment(occ = false);
  ixl : Ixl(req = {0, ...}, occ = {undef, ...}, ptSts = {undef, ...},
            ptCmd = {pundef, ...}, ma = {undef, ...});
  rmgr : RouteMgr(ar = {},
                  createTrainCnd = {true, true, true, true, true, true},
                  maReqCnd = {true, true, true, true, true, true});
  tr : Train[TMAX] = {null, null, null, null, null, null};

-- static interfaces
interface from sb10.occ to ixl.occ[b10];
interface from st10.occ to ixl.occ[t10];
interface from pt11.occ to ixl.occ[t11];
interface from st12.occ to ixl.occ[t12];
interface from pt13.occ to ixl.occ[t13];
interface from st14.occ to ixl.occ[t14];
interface from st20.occ to ixl.occ[t20];
interface from sb14.occ to ixl.occ[b14];
interface from pt11.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t11];
interface from pt13.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t13];
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t11] to pt11.ptCmd;
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t13] to pt13.ptCmd;
end collaboration

schedule
  IncomingTrain(0, c, b14, rmgr)
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 7, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <b14, t14, t13, t20>))
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 8, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <t20, t11, t10>))
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 10, rmgr); OutgoingTrain(tr[0], c, t10, b10))
  || Resolve(tr[0], 7, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[0], 8, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[0], 10, rmgr)
  || StopWithoutMA(tr[0])
  || SysTestC1_4(ixl, rmgr)
  || CoverageObserver(ixl, rmgr)
end schedule
end systemtest

```

A.2 Class 2.1 Tests

```

-----
-- Generated SCSL tests for Class 2.1: succeeding train tests
-- Source: main2.tex current templates and generation directives.
-----
-- SysTestC21_1: succeeding trains, route sequence 1.2.9
-----
elementary scenario SysTestC21_1(ixl : Ixl, rmgr : RouteMgr)

  spec G( rmgr.ar subseteq {1, 2, 9} )

  spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = b10 and X ixl.ma[0] = t12) =>
    (ixl.req[0] = 1 and
     ixl.ptCmd[t11] = plus and
     ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
     not ixl.occ[t10] and not ixl.occ[t11] and not ixl.occ[t12] and
     X (rmgr.ar = {1})) )

  spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t12 and X ixl.ma[0] = t14) =>
    (ixl.req[0] = 2 and
     ixl.ptCmd[t13] = plus and
     ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
     not ixl.occ[t13] and not ixl.occ[t14] and
     X (2 in rmgr.ar)) )

  spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t14 and X ixl.ma[0] = b14) =>
    (ixl.req[0] = 9 and
     not ixl.occ[b14] and
     X (9 in rmgr.ar)) )

  spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = b10 and X ixl.ma[1] = t12) =>
    (ixl.req[1] = 1 and
     ixl.ptCmd[t11] = plus and
     ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
     not ixl.occ[t10] and not ixl.occ[t11] and not ixl.occ[t12] and
     X (1 in rmgr.ar)) )

  spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = t12 and X ixl.ma[1] = t14) =>
    (ixl.req[1] = 2 and
     ixl.ptCmd[t13] = plus and
     ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
     not ixl.occ[t13] and not ixl.occ[t14] and
     X (2 in rmgr.ar)) )

  spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = t14 and X ixl.ma[1] = b14) =>
    (ixl.req[1] = 9 and
     not ixl.occ[b14] and
     X (9 in rmgr.ar and F (rmgr.ar = {} and X EoT))) )

  initact frm := {};
end scenario

systemtest SysTestC21_1
c : collaboration
sb10 : Segment(occ = true);
st10 : Segment(occ = false);
pt11 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = minus, ptSts = minus);
st12 : Segment(occ = false);
pt13 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = minus, ptSts = minus);
st14 : Segment(occ = false);
st20 : Segment(occ = false);
sb14 : Segment(occ = false);
ixl : Ixl(req = {0, ...}, occ = {undef, ...}, ptSts = {undef, ...},
          ptCmd = {pundef, ...}, ma = {undef, ...});
rmgr : RouteMgr(ar = {},
                createTrainCnd = {false, true, false, false, false, false},

```

```

        maReqCnd = {true, true, false, false, false, false};
tr : Train[TMAX] = {Train(pos = b10, ma = b10, req = 0), null, null, null, null, null};

-- static interfaces
interface from sb10.occ to ixl.occ[b10];
interface from st10.occ to ixl.occ[t10];
interface from pt11.occ to ixl.occ[t11];
interface from st12.occ to ixl.occ[t12];
interface from pt13.occ to ixl.occ[t13];
interface from st14.occ to ixl.occ[t14];
interface from sb14.occ to ixl.occ[b14];
interface from pt11.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t11];
interface from pt13.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t13];
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t11] to pt11.ptCmd;
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t13] to pt13.ptCmd;
-- train-IXL interfaces for trains initially residing in the network
interface from tr[0].req to ixl.req[0];
interface from ixl.ma[0] to tr[0].ma;
end collaboration

schedule
    IncomingTrain(1, c, b10, rmgr)
    || (RequestMA(0, c, 1, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <b10, t10, t11, t12>))
    || (RequestMA(0, c, 2, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <t12, t13, t14>))
    || (RequestMA(0, c, 9, rmgr); OutgoingTrain(tr[0], c, t14, b14))
    || (RequestMA(1, c, 1, rmgr); Traverse(tr[1], <b10, t10, t11, t12>))
    || (RequestMA(1, c, 2, rmgr); Traverse(tr[1], <t12, t13, t14>))
    || (RequestMA(1, c, 9, rmgr); OutgoingTrain(tr[1], c, t14, b14))
    || Resolve(tr[0], 1, rmgr)
    || Resolve(tr[0], 2, rmgr)
    || Resolve(tr[0], 9, rmgr)
    || Resolve(tr[1], 1, rmgr)
    || Resolve(tr[1], 2, rmgr)
    || Resolve(tr[1], 9, rmgr)
    || StopWithoutMA(tr[0])
    || StopWithoutMA(tr[1])
    || SysTestC21_1(ixl, rmgr)
    || CoverageObserver(ixl, rmgr)
end schedule
end systemtest

-- =====
-- SysTestC21_2: succeeding trains, route sequence 3.4.9
-- =====
elementary scenario SysTestC21_2(ixl : Ixl, rmgr : RouteMgr)

spec G( rmgr.ar subseq {3, 4, 9} )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = b10 and X ixl.ma[0] = t20) =>
    (ixl.req[0] = 3 and
    ixl.ptCmd[t11] = minus and
    ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
    not ixl.occ[t10] and not ixl.occ[t11] and not ixl.occ[t20] and
    X (rmgr.ar = {3})) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t20 and X ixl.ma[0] = t14) =>
    (ixl.req[0] = 4 and
    ixl.ptCmd[t13] = minus and
    ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
    not ixl.occ[t13] and not ixl.occ[t14] and
    X (4 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t14 and X ixl.ma[0] = b14) =>
    (ixl.req[0] = 9 and
    not ixl.occ[b14] and
    X (9 in rmgr.ar)) )

```

```

spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = b10 and X ixl.ma[1] = t20) =>
  (ixl.req[1] = 3 and
   ixl.ptCmd[t11] = minus and
   ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
   not ixl.occ[t10] and not ixl.occ[t11] and not ixl.occ[t20] and
   X (3 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = t20 and X ixl.ma[1] = t14) =>
  (ixl.req[1] = 4 and
   ixl.ptCmd[t13] = minus and
   ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
   not ixl.occ[t13] and not ixl.occ[t14] and
   X (4 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = t14 and X ixl.ma[1] = b14) =>
  (ixl.req[1] = 9 and
   not ixl.occ[b14] and
   X (9 in rmgr.ar and F (rmgr.ar = {} and X EoT))) )

initact frm := {};
end scenario

systemtest SysTestC21_2
c : collaboration
sb10 : Segment(occ = true);
st10 : Segment(occ = false);
pt11 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = plus, ptSts = plus);
st12 : Segment(occ = false);
pt13 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = plus, ptSts = plus);
st14 : Segment(occ = false);
st20 : Segment(occ = false);
sb14 : Segment(occ = false);
ixl : Ixl(req = {0, ...}, occ = {undef, ...}, ptSts = {undef, ...},
  ptCmd = {pundef, ...}, ma = {undef, ...});
rmgr : RouteMgr(ar = {},
  createTrainCnd = {false, true, false, false, false, false},
  maReqCnd = {true, true, false, false, false, false});
tr : Train[TMAX] = {Train(pos = b10, ma = b10, req = 0), null, null, null, null, null};

-- static interfaces
interface from sb10.occ to ixl.occ[b10];
interface from st10.occ to ixl.occ[t10];
interface from pt11.occ to ixl.occ[t11];
interface from st12.occ to ixl.occ[t12];
interface from pt13.occ to ixl.occ[t13];
interface from st14.occ to ixl.occ[t14];
interface from st20.occ to ixl.occ[t20];
interface from sb14.occ to ixl.occ[b14];
interface from pt11.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t11];
interface from pt13.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t13];
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t11] to pt11.ptCmd;
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t13] to pt13.ptCmd;
-- train-IXL interfaces for trains initially residing in the network
interface from tr[0].req to ixl.req[0];
interface from ixl.ma[0] to tr[0].ma;
end collaboration

schedule
  IncomingTrain(1, c, b10, rmgr)
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 3, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <b10, t10, t11, t20>))
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 4, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <t20, t13, t14>))
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 9, rmgr); OutgoingTrain(tr[0], c, t14, b14))
  || (RequestMA(1, c, 3, rmgr); Traverse(tr[1], <b10, t10, t11, t20>))
  || (RequestMA(1, c, 4, rmgr); Traverse(tr[1], <t20, t13, t14>))
  || (RequestMA(1, c, 9, rmgr); OutgoingTrain(tr[1], c, t14, b14))
  || Resolve(tr[0], 3, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[0], 4, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[0], 9, rmgr)

```

```

    || Resolve(tr[1], 3, rmgr)
    || Resolve(tr[1], 4, rmgr)
    || Resolve(tr[1], 9, rmgr)
    || StopWithoutMA(tr[0])
    || StopWithoutMA(tr[1])
    || SysTestC21_2(ixl, rmgr)
    || CoverageObserver(ixl, rmgr)
end schedule
end systemtest

-- =====
-- SysTestC21_3: succeeding trains, route sequence 5.6.10
-- =====
elementary scenario SysTestC21_3(ixl : Ixl, rmgr : RouteMgr)

spec G( rmgr.ar subseq {5, 6, 10} )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = b14 and X ixl.ma[0] = t12) =>
  (ixl.req[0] = 5 and
   ixl.ptCmd[t13] = plus and
   ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
   not ixl.occ[t14] and not ixl.occ[t13] and not ixl.occ[t12] and
   X (rmgr.ar = {5})) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t12 and X ixl.ma[0] = t10) =>
  (ixl.req[0] = 6 and
   ixl.ptCmd[t11] = plus and
   ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
   not ixl.occ[t11] and not ixl.occ[t10] and
   X (6 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t10 and X ixl.ma[0] = b10) =>
  (ixl.req[0] = 10 and
   not ixl.occ[b10] and
   X (10 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = b14 and X ixl.ma[1] = t12) =>
  (ixl.req[1] = 5 and
   ixl.ptCmd[t13] = plus and
   ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
   not ixl.occ[t14] and not ixl.occ[t13] and not ixl.occ[t12] and
   X (5 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = t12 and X ixl.ma[1] = t10) =>
  (ixl.req[1] = 6 and
   ixl.ptCmd[t11] = plus and
   ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
   not ixl.occ[t11] and not ixl.occ[t10] and
   X (6 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = t10 and X ixl.ma[1] = b10) =>
  (ixl.req[1] = 10 and
   not ixl.occ[b10] and
   X (10 in rmgr.ar and F (rmgr.ar = {} and X EoT))) )

initact frm := {};
end scenario

systemtest SysTestC21_3
c : collaboration
sb10 : Segment(occ = false);
st10 : Segment(occ = false);
pt11 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = minus, ptSts = minus);
st12 : Segment(occ = false);
pt13 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = minus, ptSts = minus);
st14 : Segment(occ = false);
st20 : Segment(occ = false);
sb14 : Segment(occ = true);

```

```

ixl : Ixl(req = {0, ...}, occ = {undef, ...}, ptSts = {undef, ...},
         ptCmd = {pundef, ...}, ma = {undef, ...});
rmgr : RouteMgr(ar = {},
               createTrainCmd = {false, true, false, false, false, false},
               maReqCmd = {true, true, false, false, false, false});
tr : Train[TMAX] = {Train(pos = b14, ma = b14, req = 0), null, null, null, null};

-- static interfaces
interface from sb10.occ to ixl.occ[b10];
interface from st10.occ to ixl.occ[t10];
interface from pt11.occ to ixl.occ[t11];
interface from st12.occ to ixl.occ[t12];
interface from pt13.occ to ixl.occ[t13];
interface from st14.occ to ixl.occ[t14];
interface from st20.occ to ixl.occ[t20];
interface from sb14.occ to ixl.occ[b14];
interface from pt11.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t11];
interface from pt13.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t13];
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t11] to pt11.ptCmd;
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t13] to pt13.ptCmd;
-- train-IXL interfaces for trains initially residing in the network
interface from tr[0].req to ixl.req[0];
interface from ixl.ma[0] to tr[0].ma;
end collaboration

schedule
  IncomingTrain(1, c, b14, rmgr)
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 5, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <b14, t14, t13, t12>))
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 6, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <t12, t11, t10>))
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 10, rmgr); OutgoingTrain(tr[0], c, t10, b10))
  || (RequestMA(1, c, 5, rmgr); Traverse(tr[1], <b14, t14, t13, t12>))
  || (RequestMA(1, c, 6, rmgr); Traverse(tr[1], <t12, t11, t10>))
  || (RequestMA(1, c, 10, rmgr); OutgoingTrain(tr[1], c, t10, b10))
  || Resolve(tr[0], 5, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[0], 6, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[0], 10, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[1], 5, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[1], 6, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[1], 10, rmgr)
  || StopWithoutMA(tr[0])
  || StopWithoutMA(tr[1])
  || SysTestC21_3(ixl, rmgr)
  || CoverageObserver(ixl, rmgr)
end schedule
end systemtest

-- =====
-- SysTestC21_4: succeeding trains, route sequence 7.8.10
-- =====
elementary scenario SysTestC21_4(ixl : Ixl, rmgr : RouteMgr)

spec G( rmgr.ar subseq {7, 8, 10} )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = b14 and X ixl.ma[0] = t20) =>
  (ixl.req[0] = 7 and
   ixl.ptCmd[t13] = minus and
   ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
   not ixl.occ[t14] and not ixl.occ[t13] and not ixl.occ[t20] and
   X (rmgr.ar = {7})) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t20 and X ixl.ma[0] = t10) =>
  (ixl.req[0] = 8 and
   ixl.ptCmd[t11] = minus and
   ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
   not ixl.occ[t11] and not ixl.occ[t10] and
   X (8 in rmgr.ar) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t10 and X ixl.ma[0] = b10) =>

```

```

(ixl.req[0] = 10 and
not ixl.occ[b10] and
X (10 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = b14 and X ixl.ma[1] = t20) =>
(ixl.req[1] = 7 and
ixl.ptCmd[t13] = minus and
ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
not ixl.occ[t14] and not ixl.occ[t13] and not ixl.occ[t20] and
X (7 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = t20 and X ixl.ma[1] = t10) =>
(ixl.req[1] = 8 and
ixl.ptCmd[t11] = minus and
ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
not ixl.occ[t11] and not ixl.occ[t10] and
X (8 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = t10 and X ixl.ma[1] = b10) =>
(ixl.req[1] = 10 and
not ixl.occ[b10] and
X (10 in rmgr.ar and F (rmgr.ar = {}) and X EoT))) )

initact frm := {};
end scenario

systemtest SysTestC21_4
c : collaboration
sb10 : Segment(occ = false);
st10 : Segment(occ = false);
pt11 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = plus, ptSts = plus);
st12 : Segment(occ = false);
pt13 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = plus, ptSts = plus);
st14 : Segment(occ = false);
st20 : Segment(occ = false);
sb14 : Segment(occ = true);
ixl : Ixl(req = {0, ...}, occ = {undef, ...}, ptSts = {undef, ...},
ptCmd = {pundef, ...}, ma = {undef, ...});
rmgr : RouteMgr(ar = {},
createTrainCnd = {false, true, false, false, false, false},
maReqCnd = {true, true, false, false, false, false});
tr : Train[TMAX] = {Train(pos = b14, ma = b14, req = 0), null, null, null, null, null};

-- static interfaces
interface from sb10.occ to ixl.occ[b10];
interface from st10.occ to ixl.occ[t10];
interface from pt11.occ to ixl.occ[t11];
interface from st12.occ to ixl.occ[t12];
interface from pt13.occ to ixl.occ[t13];
interface from st14.occ to ixl.occ[t14];
interface from st20.occ to ixl.occ[t20];
interface from sb14.occ to ixl.occ[b14];
interface from pt11.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t11];
interface from pt13.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t13];
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t11] to pt11.ptCmd;
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t13] to pt13.ptCmd;
-- train-IXL interfaces for trains initially residing in the network
interface from tr[0].req to ixl.req[0];
interface from ixl.ma[0] to tr[0].ma;
end collaboration

schedule
IncomingTrain(1, c, b14, rmgr)
|| (RequestMA(0, c, 7, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <b14, t14, t13, t20>))
|| (RequestMA(0, c, 8, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <t20, t11, t10>))
|| (RequestMA(0, c, 10, rmgr); OutgoingTrain(tr[0], c, t10, b10))
|| (RequestMA(1, c, 7, rmgr); Traverse(tr[1], <b14, t14, t13, t20>))
|| (RequestMA(1, c, 8, rmgr); Traverse(tr[1], <t20, t11, t10>))

```

```

    || (RequestMA(1, c, 10, rmgr); OutgoingTrain(tr[1], c, t10, b10))
    || Resolve(tr[0], 7, rmgr)
    || Resolve(tr[0], 8, rmgr)
    || Resolve(tr[0], 10, rmgr)
    || Resolve(tr[1], 7, rmgr)
    || Resolve(tr[1], 8, rmgr)
    || Resolve(tr[1], 10, rmgr)
    || StopWithoutMA(tr[0])
    || StopWithoutMA(tr[1])
    || SysTestC21_4(ixl, rmgr)
    || CoverageObserver(ixl, rmgr)
end schedule
end systemtest

```

A.3 Class 2.2 Tests

```

-- =====
-- Generated SCSL tests for Class 2.2: conflicting route tests
-- Source: main2.tex current templates and generation directives.
-- =====
-- SysTestC22_1: three-train conflicting routes, covered conflicts (1,8) and (2,7)
-- =====
elementary scenario SysTestC22_1(ixl : Ixl, rmgr : RouteMgr)

precondition 8 in ixlTbl[1].conf and 7 in ixlTbl[2].conf;

spec G( rmgr.ar subseq {1, 2, 8, 7} and
        not ({1, 8} subseq rmgr.ar) and
        not ({2, 7} subseq rmgr.ar) )

spec rmgr.maReqCnd[0] U
    (ixl.req[0] = 1 and not rmgr.maReqCnd[0] and
     (not rmgr.maReqCnd[0]) U (7 in rmgr.ar and G rmgr.maReqCnd[0]) )

spec (not rmgr.maReqCnd[1]) U (1 in rmgr.ar and G rmgr.maReqCnd[1])

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = b10 and X ixl.ma[0] = t12) =>
    (ixl.req[0] = 1 and
     ixl.ptCmd[t11] = plus and
     ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
     not ixl.occ[t10] and not ixl.occ[t11] and not ixl.occ[t12] and
     X (1 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t12 and X ixl.ma[0] = t14) =>
    (ixl.req[0] = 2 and
     ixl.ptCmd[t13] = plus and
     ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
     not ixl.occ[t13] and not ixl.occ[t14] and
     X (2 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = t20 and X ixl.ma[1] = t10) =>
    (ixl.req[1] = 8 and
     ixl.ptCmd[t11] = minus and
     ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
     not ixl.occ[t11] and not ixl.occ[t10] and
     X (8 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[2] = b14 and X ixl.ma[2] = t20) =>
    (ixl.req[2] = 7 and
     ixl.ptCmd[t13] = minus and
     ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
     not ixl.occ[t14] and not ixl.occ[t13] and not ixl.occ[t20] and
     X (7 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( 2 in rmgr.ar and X (2 notin rmgr.ar) => X X EoT )

```

```

initact frm := { rmgr.maReqCnd[0], rmgr.maReqCnd[1] };
end scenario

systemtest SysTestC22_1
  c : collaboration
    sb10 : Segment(occ = true);
    st10 : Segment(occ = false);
    pt11 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = plus, ptSts = plus);
    st12 : Segment(occ = false);
    pt13 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = plus, ptSts = plus);
    st14 : Segment(occ = false);
    st20 : Segment(occ = true);
    sb14 : Segment(occ = true);
    ixl : Ixl(req = {0, ...}, occ = {undef, ...}, ptSts = {undef, ...},
              ptCmd = {pundef, ...}, ma = {undef, ...});
    rmgr : RouteMgr(ar = {},
                   createTrainCnd = {false, false, false, false, false, false},
                   maReqCnd = {true, false, true, false, false, false});
    tr : Train[TMAX] = {Train(pos = b10, ma = b10, req = 0),
                       Train(pos = t20, ma = t20, req = 0),
                       Train(pos = b14, ma = b14, req = 0), null, null, null};

    -- static interfaces
    interface from sb10.occ to ixl.occ[b10];
    interface from st10.occ to ixl.occ[t10];
    interface from pt11.occ to ixl.occ[t11];
    interface from st12.occ to ixl.occ[t12];
    interface from pt13.occ to ixl.occ[t13];
    interface from st14.occ to ixl.occ[t14];
    interface from st20.occ to ixl.occ[t20];
    interface from sb14.occ to ixl.occ[b14];
    interface from pt11.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t11];
    interface from pt13.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t13];
    interface from ixl.ptCmd[t11] to pt11.ptCmd;
    interface from ixl.ptCmd[t13] to pt13.ptCmd;
    -- train-IXL interfaces for trains initially residing in the network
    interface from tr[0].req to ixl.req[0];
    interface from tr[1].req to ixl.req[1];
    interface from tr[2].req to ixl.req[2];
    interface from ixl.ma[0] to tr[0].ma;
    interface from ixl.ma[1] to tr[1].ma;
    interface from ixl.ma[2] to tr[2].ma;
  end collaboration

  schedule
    (RequestMA(0, c, 1, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <b10, t10, t11, t12>))
    || (RequestMA(0, c, 2, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <t12, t13, t14>))
    || (RequestMA(1, c, 8, rmgr); Traverse(tr[1], <t20, t11, t10>))
    || (RequestMA(2, c, 7, rmgr); Traverse(tr[2], <b14, t14, t13, t20>))
    || Resolve(tr[0], 1, rmgr)
    || Resolve(tr[0], 2, rmgr)
    || Resolve(tr[1], 8, rmgr)
    || Resolve(tr[2], 7, rmgr)
    || StopWithoutMA(tr[0])
    || StopWithoutMA(tr[1])
    || StopWithoutMA(tr[2])
    || SysTestC22_1(ixl, rmgr)
    || CoverageObserver(ixl, rmgr)
  end schedule
end systemtest

-- =====
-- SysTestC22_2: three-train conflicting routes, covered conflicts (3,6) and (4,5)
-- =====
elementary scenario SysTestC22_2(ixl : Ixl, rmgr : RouteMgr)

  precondition 6 in ixlTbl[3].conf and 5 in ixlTbl[4].conf;

```

```

spec G( rmgr.ar subseq {3, 4, 6, 5} and
  not ({3, 6} subseq rmgr.ar) and
  not ({4, 5} subseq rmgr.ar) )

spec rmgr.maReqCnd[0] U
  (ixl.req[0] = 3 and not rmgr.maReqCnd[0] and
   (not rmgr.maReqCnd[0]) U (5 in rmgr.ar and G rmgr.maReqCnd[0]))

spec (not rmgr.maReqCnd[1]) U (3 in rmgr.ar and G rmgr.maReqCnd[1])

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = b10 and X ixl.ma[0] = t20) =>
  (ixl.req[0] = 3 and
   ixl.ptCmd[t11] = minus and
   ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
   not ixl.occ[t10] and not ixl.occ[t11] and not ixl.occ[t20] and
   X (3 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t20 and X ixl.ma[0] = t14) =>
  (ixl.req[0] = 4 and
   ixl.ptCmd[t13] = minus and
   ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
   not ixl.occ[t13] and not ixl.occ[t14] and
   X (4 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = t12 and X ixl.ma[1] = t10) =>
  (ixl.req[1] = 6 and
   ixl.ptCmd[t11] = plus and
   ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
   not ixl.occ[t11] and not ixl.occ[t10] and
   X (6 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[2] = b14 and X ixl.ma[2] = t12) =>
  (ixl.req[2] = 5 and
   ixl.ptCmd[t13] = plus and
   ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
   not ixl.occ[t14] and not ixl.occ[t13] and not ixl.occ[t12] and
   X (5 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( 4 in rmgr.ar and X (4 notin rmgr.ar) => X X EoT )

inactv frm := { rmgr.maReqCnd[0], rmgr.maReqCnd[1] };
end scenario

systemtest SysTestC22_2
c : collaboration
sb10 : Segment(occ = true);
st10 : Segment(occ = false);
pt11 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = minus, ptSts = minus);
st12 : Segment(occ = true);
pt13 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = minus, ptSts = minus);
st14 : Segment(occ = false);
st20 : Segment(occ = false);
sb14 : Segment(occ = true);
ixl : Ixl(req = {0, ...}, occ = {undef, ...}, ptSts = {undef, ...},
  ptCmd = {pundef, ...}, ma = {undef, ...});
rmgr : RouteMgr(ar = {},
  createTrainCnd = {false, false, false, false, false, false},
  maReqCnd = {true, false, true, false, false, false});
tr : Train[TMAX] = {Train(pos = b10, ma = b10, req = 0),
  Train(pos = t12, ma = t12, req = 0),
  Train(pos = b14, ma = b14, req = 0), null, null, null};

-- static interfaces
interface from sb10.occ to ixl.occ[b10];
interface from st10.occ to ixl.occ[t10];
interface from pt11.occ to ixl.occ[t11];
interface from st12.occ to ixl.occ[t12];
interface from pt13.occ to ixl.occ[t13];

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interface from st14.occ to ixl.occ[t14];
interface from st20.occ to ixl.occ[t20];
interface from sb14.occ to ixl.occ[b14];
interface from pt11.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t11];
interface from pt13.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t13];
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t11] to pt11.ptCmd;
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t13] to pt13.ptCmd;
-- train-IXL interfaces for trains initially residing in the network
interface from tr[0].req to ixl.req[0];
interface from tr[1].req to ixl.req[1];
interface from tr[2].req to ixl.req[2];
interface from ixl.ma[0] to tr[0].ma;
interface from ixl.ma[1] to tr[1].ma;
interface from ixl.ma[2] to tr[2].ma;
end collaboration

schedule
  (RequestMA(0, c, 3, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <b10, t10, t11, t20>))
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 4, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <t20, t13, t14>))
  || (RequestMA(1, c, 6, rmgr); Traverse(tr[1], <t12, t11, t10>))
  || (RequestMA(2, c, 5, rmgr); Traverse(tr[2], <b14, t14, t13, t12>))
  || Resolve(tr[0], 3, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[0], 4, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[1], 6, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[2], 5, rmgr)
  || StopWithoutMA(tr[0])
  || StopWithoutMA(tr[1])
  || StopWithoutMA(tr[2])
  || SysTestC22_2(ixl, rmgr)
  || CoverageObserver(ixl, rmgr)
end schedule
end systemtest

-- =====
-- SysTestC22_3: two-train conflicting routes, covered conflict (2,4)
-- =====
elementary scenario SysTestC22_3(ixl : Ixl, rmgr : RouteMgr)

precondition 4 in ixlTbl[2].conf;

spec G( rmgr.ar subseteq {2, 9, 4} and not ({2, 4} subseteq rmgr.ar))

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t12 and X ixl.ma[0] = t14) =>
  (ixl.req[0] = 2 and
   ixl.ptCmd[t13] = plus and
   ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
   not ixl.occ[t13] and not ixl.occ[t14] and
   X (2 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t14 and X ixl.ma[0] = b14) =>
  (ixl.req[0] = 9 and
   not ixl.occ[b14] and
   X (9 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = t20 and X ixl.ma[1] = t14) =>
  (ixl.req[1] = 4 and
   ixl.ptCmd[t13] = minus and
   ixl.ptSts[t13] = ixl.ptCmd[t13] and
   not ixl.occ[t13] and not ixl.occ[t14] and
   X (4 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = t14 and X ixl.ma[1] = b14) =>
  (ixl.req[1] = 9 and
   not ixl.occ[b14] and
   X (9 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (not ixl.occ[b10] and not ixl.occ[t10] and
  not ixl.occ[t11] and not ixl.occ[t12] and

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    not ixl.occ[t13] and not ixl.occ[t14] and
    not ixl.occ[t20] and not ixl.occ[b14]) => X EoT )

initact frm := {};
end scenario

systemtest SysTestC22_3
c : collaboration
  sb10 : Segment(occ = false);
  st10 : Segment(occ = false);
  pt11 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = plus, ptSts = plus);
  st12 : Segment(occ = true);
  pt13 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = plus, ptSts = plus);
  st14 : Segment(occ = false);
  st20 : Segment(occ = true);
  sb14 : Segment(occ = false);
  ixl : Ixl(req = {0, ...}, occ = {undef, ...}, ptSts = {undef, ...},
    ptCmd = {pundef, ...}, ma = {undef, ...});
  rmgr : RouteMgr(ar = {}),
    createTrainCnd = {false, false, false, false, false, false},
    maReqCnd = {true, true, false, false, false, false});
  tr : Train[TMAX] = {Train(pos = t12, ma = t12, req = 0),
    Train(pos = t20, ma = t20, req = 0), null, null, null, null};

-- static interfaces
interface from sb10.occ to ixl.occ[b10];
interface from st10.occ to ixl.occ[t10];
interface from pt11.occ to ixl.occ[t11];
interface from st12.occ to ixl.occ[t12];
interface from pt13.occ to ixl.occ[t13];
interface from st14.occ to ixl.occ[t14];
interface from st20.occ to ixl.occ[t20];
interface from sb14.occ to ixl.occ[b14];
interface from pt11.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t11];
interface from pt13.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t13];
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t11] to pt11.ptCmd;
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t13] to pt13.ptCmd;
-- train-IXL interfaces for trains initially residing in the network
interface from tr[0].req to ixl.req[0];
interface from tr[1].req to ixl.req[1];
interface from ixl.ma[0] to tr[0].ma;
interface from ixl.ma[1] to tr[1].ma;
end collaboration

schedule
  (RequestMA(0, c, 2, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <t12, t13, t14>))
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 9, rmgr); OutgoingTrain(tr[0], c, t14, b14))
  || (RequestMA(1, c, 4, rmgr); Traverse(tr[1], <t20, t13, t14>))
  || (RequestMA(1, c, 9, rmgr); OutgoingTrain(tr[1], c, t14, b14))
  || Resolve(tr[0], 2, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[0], 9, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[1], 4, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[1], 9, rmgr)
  || StopWithoutMA(tr[0])
  || StopWithoutMA(tr[1])
  || SysTestC22_3(ixl, rmgr)
  || CoverageObserver(ixl, rmgr)
end schedule
end systemtest

-- =====
-- SysTestC22_4: two-train conflicting routes, covered conflict (6,8)
-- =====
elementary scenario SysTestC22_4(ixl : Ixl, rmgr : RouteMgr)

precondition 8 in ixlTbl[6].conf;

spec G( rmgr.ar subseq {6, 10, 8} and not ({6, 8} subseq rmgr.ar ) )

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```

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t12 and X ixl.ma[0] = t10) =>
  (ixl.req[0] = 6 and
   ixl.ptCmd[t11] = plus and
   ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
   not ixl.occ[t11] and not ixl.occ[t10] and
   X (6 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[0] = t10 and X ixl.ma[0] = b10) =>
  (ixl.req[0] = 10 and
   not ixl.occ[b10] and
   X (10 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = t20 and X ixl.ma[1] = t10) =>
  (ixl.req[1] = 8 and
   ixl.ptCmd[t11] = minus and
   ixl.ptSts[t11] = ixl.ptCmd[t11] and
   not ixl.occ[t11] and not ixl.occ[t10] and
   X (8 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (ixl.ma[1] = t10 and X ixl.ma[1] = b10) =>
  (ixl.req[1] = 10 and
   not ixl.occ[b10] and
   X (10 in rmgr.ar)) )

spec G( (not ixl.occ[b10] and not ixl.occ[t10] and
  not ixl.occ[t11] and not ixl.occ[t12] and
  not ixl.occ[t13] and not ixl.occ[t14] and
  not ixl.occ[t20] and not ixl.occ[b14]) => X EoT )

initact frm := {};
end scenario

systemtest SysTestC22_4
c : collaboration
  sb10 : Segment(occ = false);
  st10 : Segment(occ = false);
  pt11 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = minus, ptSts = minus);
  st12 : Segment(occ = true);
  pt13 : Point(occ = false, ptCmd = minus, ptSts = minus);
  st14 : Segment(occ = false);
  st20 : Segment(occ = true);
  sb14 : Segment(occ = false);
  ixl : Ixl(req = {0, ...}, occ = {undef, ...}, ptSts = {undef, ...},
    ptCmd = {pundef, ...}, ma = {undef, ...});
  rmgr : RouteMgr(ar = {},
    createTrainCnd = {false, false, false, false, false, false},
    maReqCnd = {true, true, false, false, false, false});
  tr : Train[TMAX] = {Train(pos = t12, ma = t12, req = 0),
    Train(pos = t20, ma = t20, req = 0), null, null, null, null};

-- static interfaces
interface from sb10.occ to ixl.occ[b10];
interface from st10.occ to ixl.occ[t10];
interface from pt11.occ to ixl.occ[t11];
interface from st12.occ to ixl.occ[t12];
interface from pt13.occ to ixl.occ[t13];
interface from st14.occ to ixl.occ[t14];
interface from st20.occ to ixl.occ[t20];
interface from sb14.occ to ixl.occ[b14];
interface from pt11.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t11];
interface from pt13.ptSts to ixl.ptSts[t13];
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t11] to pt11.ptCmd;
interface from ixl.ptCmd[t13] to pt13.ptCmd;
-- train-IXL interfaces for trains initially residing in the network
interface from tr[0].req to ixl.req[0];
interface from tr[1].req to ixl.req[1];
interface from ixl.ma[0] to tr[0].ma;

```

```
    interface from ixl.ma[1] to tr[1].ma;
end collaboration

schedule
  (RequestMA(0, c, 6, rmgr); Traverse(tr[0], <t12, t11, t10>))
  || (RequestMA(0, c, 10, rmgr); OutgoingTrain(tr[0], c, t10, b10))
  || (RequestMA(1, c, 8, rmgr); Traverse(tr[1], <t20, t11, t10>))
  || (RequestMA(1, c, 10, rmgr); OutgoingTrain(tr[1], c, t10, b10))
  || Resolve(tr[0], 6, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[0], 10, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[1], 8, rmgr)
  || Resolve(tr[1], 10, rmgr)
  || StopWithoutMA(tr[0])
  || StopWithoutMA(tr[1])
  || SysTestC22_4(ixl, rmgr)
  || CoverageObserver(ixl, rmgr)
end schedule
end systemtest
```